

Efficient trustworthy AI - making the best of data (AI, Data and Robotics Partnership)
(RIA)

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PANDORA

A Comprehensive Framework enabling the Delivery of
Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation

D7.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ADRA	AI, Data and Robotics Association
AlaaS	AI as a Service
AIoD	AI on Demand
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of things
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BoD	Board of Directors
CaaS	Computation as a Service
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DGA	Data Governance Act
DSBA	Data Spaces Business Alliance
DSSC	Data Space Support Center
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FL	Federated Learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
HPC	High Performance Computing
IPCEI	Important Projects of Common European Interest
IT	Information Technology
JU	Joint Undertaking
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
NoE	Network of (AI) Excellence
PC	Project Coordinator
PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology
QGRB	Quality Assurance, Gender Equality, and Risk Management Board
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SRIDA	Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda
TAM	Total Addressable Market
USA	United States of America
USP	Unique Selling Proposition

WP Work Package
XAI eXplainable AI

Executive Summary

It was some days ago, before the submission of this report, that Ursula Von Der Leyen, President of the European Commission, presented the so-called Competitiveness Compass proposal, a plan to revamp the European Economy. Coincidentally, this occurred around key announcements in the AI field: first, the United States unveiled a \$500 billion AI infrastructure plan to drive innovation. Just a few days later, China introduced the DeepSeek AI model, capable of competing with ChatGPT while consuming less energy and requiring significantly lower investment.

Where is Europe in all this? For Europe to stay in this race, which is not only a technological one but a question of economic survival, our continent will have to make great investments in computing power, cloud infrastructure and access to data. So far, considerable funding has been devoted to creating **AI factories and AI-optimised supercomputers**. The focus now will be on the realization of a **cloud and AI development plan** to enable the **training of very large AI models**, as well as **increase adoption of AI by companies**.

The career to stay at the forefront of AI will necessarily require **access to vast amounts of data**, and here is where concepts like data sharing enabled by data spaces and other platforms are relevant, but also and very importantly is the **generation of high-quality synthetic data**. That is why PANDORA comes as a great added value to this picture, and this is just a partial angle of the project.

PANDORA has defined a comprehensive work plan that embraces some of the most challenging technical aspects, but **in D7.1, the document you are reading now, we argue that other activities and decisions that do not fall under technology development are equally important to guarantee the success of the project looking at recognition and adoption of the project results**. WP7 brings complementarity to technical activities (architecture, development of tools and even deployment of pilots) thanks to a focus on **marketing, exploitation-related activities, clustering and international cooperation to maximize the impact of the project**.

D7.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation, is the first document of a series of reports that will be released by WP7. As the first one, it depicts the strategy of the project in that regard and outlines key strategic activities to be implemented during the course of the PANDORA project. In particular, the activities revolve around four major pillars:

- **Dissemination & Communication** – It includes branding, production of marketing materials and use of digital channels such as the project website, social media and newsletters, besides the planning for events, workshops and other dissemination vehicles.
- **Exploitation & Adoption of Results** – Ensuring AI adoption in the AIoT space through market analysis, competitive positioning, and the definition of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The later phase focuses on market segmentation and a go-to-market strategy.
- **Collaboration & Networking** – Building relationships with EC-funded projects, associations, and organizations with initial efforts on project awareness, while later stages will aim at commercial and strategic partnerships.
- **International Cooperation** – Engaging in selective global partnerships that add strategic value to the project while optimising resource allocation.

D7.1 details the rationale behind these activities, summarizing work completed from April to December 2024 and specifying the next steps.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document is the first report generated by WP7 in PANDORA and aims to define the strategy of the project around the use of mechanisms like marketing, market-related activities, clustering and international cooperation to maximize the impact of the project.

It is an initial report because some of the decisions are still being taken by the project and further developments may be expected in the next months, impacting the formulation of messages from PANDORA to external constituencies. Therefore, it should be understood as the initial version that will evolve according to the project needs.

D7.1 includes the overall approach for impact creation with the description of strategic and operational aspects in the four major pillars of this WP:

- **Dissemination and communication:** it is important to make the distinction between communication actions of a more general character, and dissemination activities, which require a suitable segmentation of target audiences and the corresponding adaptation of messages and channels depending on the goals towards those audiences. While at the beginning of the project communication is as important as dissemination -sometimes more, the weight of dissemination activities normally increases with the project lifetime, becoming a perfect complement to exploitation in the later phases of the project.
- **Exploitation and adoption of project results.** While understanding the challenges of the topics addressed by the project are important for the scientific community, the pilots in the project and the technical approach have been defined not only to research and validate technologies, but also to foster the adoption of AI in the AIoT environment. A good understanding of the requirements and needs of stakeholders in our demonstrators, but also of the wider potential market for PANDORA, is essential to ensure coherence and alignment of our work with what the market demands. In the initial phase of the project this requires work along activities such as market analysis, accounting for competition in both commercial and pre-commercial environments, definition of the right positioning based on a detailed characterization of PANDORA and the definition of its KERs, deriving a clear value proposition or USP that makes our results competitive in a market overloaded with products and solutions. The second part of the project -once the maturity of expected results allow- will require updates of the market analysis but looking at proper definition of the segments PANDORA will address and if feasible, the definition of a model to assess the Total Addressable Market (TAM); this should be the starting point of the design of a go-to-market strategy, where other decisions like branding, licensing, pricing, business model(s) will be of paramount importance.
- **Collaboration, networking and clustering.** Activities falling under this name entail the creation of relationships that are useful for PANDORA to achieve its results. To give an example, we will collaborate with projects funded by the EC under the same area as PANDORA, as well as others for which an added value can be derived. Collaboration means also reaching out to initiatives, associations, and organizations that may be needed by the project to be successful from different points of view, including technical development and notably exploitation and use of project results. As such, we could say that these activities are enablers for dissemination and project awareness, exploitation - and even international cooperation, and thus, they work in tight cooperation with the former ones. The first part of the project will be characterized by relationships that help to create awareness around PANDORA and clarify its positioning in the value chain and the research ecosystem. It is expected that the second part will also add elements looking at

potential commercial relationships and strategic partnerships to scale, as described later in this document.

- **International cooperation:** this is also a variation of some of the activities described so far, but adding the international dimension as part of its nature. In that regard, the objectives may vary. PANDORA will seek for synergies and cooperations that add value to the project from a strategic point of view as it needs to carefully measure the resources assigned to these activities. The global ecosystem requires deliberate thoughts on which countries and stakeholders will act as catalysts for Europe and which ones will not.

D7.1 describes the rationale behind all these activities and provides the reader with a picture of the work that has already been executed in the course of the project (basically from April 2024 until the end of the same year) and the steps that will follow based on our strategic approach.

1.2 Intended readership

The target audience of this document is twofold:

- **PANDORA partners:** the document should help the entire consortium to get a clear view of our strategy, be able to follow the operational plans, and contribute to them in a coherent and consistent manner from their tasks and WPs. Similarly, they should provide this WP with the right input not only in terms of technical evolution of the project, but also by sharing any element that they consider important for the right formulation of the project impact strategy.
- **External stakeholders:** any organization not directly involved in PANDORA that finds the project interesting and relevant to their work and wishes to understand the ways to engage with us through the several activities introduced above.

1.3 Relationship with other PANDORA WPs and managerial organization

WP7 works hand-in-hand with all the other WPs in the project, since the content needed to carry out these activities is generated within technical WPs. However, WP7 is instrumental in increasing the potential impact of the project, as described in our proposal and therefore, not only look at high levels of scientific and technical quality of the expected outcomes in isolation, but in the context of the market demands and European competitiveness. This obviously requires the project to be well-known in the community, to establish relationships for different types of synergies, to define a suitable value proposition that helps stakeholders to understand in clear terms what PANDORA is and offers, how it can be used and under which terms and conditions- ultimately leading to the successful adoption of some or all of the project results.

D7.1 will be complemented by D7.2 “Communication activities, synergies and scientific inclusion”, and D7.3 “PANDORA business model and long-term sustainability report”. The activities implemented during the project across the four types of work described above will be documented in both reports at the end of the project (M36). One of the reports will highlight the dissemination effort, while the other will focus more on the exploitation aspects of the project.

2. Main pillars for Impact Maximization

2.1 Context

PANDORA, as described in its contract, envisages a wide array of potential impacts that, in many cases, depend on the successful execution of the proposed technical work (whether in architecture, technology development, or deployment in pilot settings), but it is normally the case that other elements need to be in place to ensure that the impact can materialize. In fact, the technical work of the project leads to performance indicators, while other activities normally are at the intersection of the impact indicators. Mature readers may remember the emergence of video reproducers around 40-50 years ago.

The competition between Betamax (Beta) and VHS in the late 1970s and early 1980s was a classic example of a format war, where two incompatible technologies competed for market dominance. Sony introduced Betamax in 1975, offering superior video quality and a more compact cassette. However, JVC's VHS, launched in 1976, quickly gained an edge due to longer recording times, lower costs, and a more open licensing strategy, allowing multiple manufacturers to produce VHS players. As more studios and rental stores adopted VHS due to its affordability and wider availability, consumers followed. By the mid-1980s, VHS had effectively won the battle, and Betamax became a niche product before fading out entirely. This case remains a landmark in market adoption dynamics, illustrating how network effects, licensing strategies, and consumer convenience often outweigh technical superiority.

This is a very clear example of how decisions that belong to how to position a product in the market and not just to technical excellence make the difference between success and failure. At the time of writing this report, none of them are widely used anymore (even though still in place for nostalgic users) and streaming is the way to consume video by most people.

The rationale and the message behind this example are clear. All projects, including PANDORA, need to go beyond the technical work to ensure survival in one way or another after the project's completion.

WP7 provides the framework where marketing and dissemination, market analysis, and exploitation strategies, establishment of strategic alliances and clustering and international cooperation will all work for that "extra" ingredient that makes PANDORA valuable beyond the project concept.

2.2 Expected Impact

The four pillars of WP7 in conjunction with other WPs should provide the path towards the following expected impacts and, ultimately, motivation to invest in PANDORA:

- Increased inclusiveness, by supporting a human-centered approach to technology development that is aligned with social and ethical values.
- High-quality jobs by targeting skills mismatches, the need to empower workers including those at risk of social exclusion.

Sustainable AI, referring to less energy consumption and environmental footprint.

These impacts reflect the potential long-term effect of using the results produced by PANDORA and in fact, some of them require intermediate steps that are linked to activities defined in WP7. For example, the second point signals the organization of 7 info days and workshops and at least 6 collaborations with International and European organizations and scientific communities. Thus, we see the enabling role of WP7.

The most relevant impacts, however, come before the long-term impacts, and they should result as an effect of triggering specific measures in the project in the four areas of work of WP7, accompanied by the right content from technical WPs. The expected outcomes and their performance will be followed by us and converted into the right messages and selling points, and, when possible, benchmarks will apply so that a more credible approach can be presented to users from outside the project. In addition, and under our responsibility, specific points can be highlighted as follows:

- The **branding** and the name of the project should be **easily recognizable** by the research communities working in AI and the topics tackled by PANDORA.
- Sister projects and overall, AI-related projects and associations should know and understand what the **offering of PANDORA** is (what is it, what are the differences in comparison to other projects, why is it relevant and differential?)
- The **portfolio of exploitable results** (commonly known as KER) should be clearly characterized and defined, with accompanying information about functionalities, licenses, business model(s), ownership and terms and conditions of use.
- A **sound go-to-market strategy** should be available at the end of the project, including an updated market analysis, competitors' landscape, concept validation, selection of target markets (with TAM, if possible), financial model, marketing strategy for the post-project phase, identified value chain and role(s) of partners among those interested in joining an exploitation agreement, etc.
- Collaborations should have been established with major players with concrete goals, including **partnership agreements and alliances** for adoption purposes in the last part of the project.

2.3 Pillars of the strategy: high level view or how to achieve Impact

In order for PANDORA to define and implement the right paths towards the former list of expected impacts, the following ingredients are part of our strategy:

- **Clear Alignment with EU Priorities & Policy Goals:** this entails considering the evolution of Horizon Europe (HE) priorities such as Green Deal, and especially ongoing **policy development** (e.g., standards, regulations, where Data Act, DGA or AI Act); strengthening European **technological sovereignty and competitiveness**.
- **Strong Multi-Stakeholder Engagement:** Involvement of **industry, SMEs, policymakers, and civil society** from the start; effective **co-creation** and consultation with end-users; well-structured **public-private and/or private-private partnerships** to ensure adoption beyond academia.
- **Tangible Economic & Market Impact:** development of **scalable and exploitable results** (e.g., patents, prototypes, spin-offs), strong **exploitation strategies** involving industry and entrepreneurs; focus on **technology transfer** and commercialisation pathways.
- **Messaging developed not only about technology aspects but also about Societal & Environmental Benefits:** contribution to **societal challenges** (climate change, high-quality manufacturing, skills, etc.); measurable impact on **citizens' well-being** and quality of life; support for **sustainability** and responsible research principles (a bit aligned with the first point of the list).
- **High-Quality Dissemination & Communication:** Open-access publications, FAIR data principles, and broad knowledge sharing; Strategic **media outreach**, policy briefs, and stakeholder engagement; Use of **European and international networks** to amplify visibility.

All these elements are present in one or several of the 4 action lines of WP7 (corresponding to the tasks in our work plan as follows, and briefly explained in section 1.1:

- Dissemination and communication (T7.2)
- Exploitation and adoption of project results (T7.6)
- Collaboration, networking and clustering (T7.3, T7.4)
- International cooperation (T7.5)

3. Overview of the market and trends: the context for PANDORA

This section provides a preliminary overview of the technology market looking at the main priorities of PANDORA. It is based on an extensive survey conducted by IDC for the Unlock.cei¹ project, combined with additional proprietary data from IDC. It will be revisited, refined, and updated as needed for very specific market segments selected by the project.

3.1 IoT market

European industries are embracing solutions that leverage IoT devices and AI analytics to achieve increased efficiency, sustainability, reliability and automation of industrial processes and infrastructure.

The adoption of these technologies and solutions is rapidly rising. Most companies across the European economy are familiar with IoT and its benefits, and in a survey of European companies in selected industries led by IDC in March 2023, 51% said they were already using IoT, while another 21% planned to do so. Moreover, in the manufacturing sector, adoption was even higher with 56% already using IoT (see figure 1).

Figure 1: IoT Usage by Industry (source: UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)

As a result of this widespread adoption, the IoT market in Europe is estimated to already account for EUR 231 billion in 2024, with a compound annual growth rate to 2028 or 11.2%. The manufacturing sector is one of the largest segments of this market, representing EUR 66 billion in 2024. (source: IDC's Worldwide Internet of Things Spending Guide, May 2024).

Companies seek a range of benefits from these solutions. In this survey, the top business outcome expected from IoT projects was efficiency and productivity. Beyond making more with less, companies also expect many other benefits, including improved customer experience, better decision-making, reaching new customer segments, improved safety, launching new products, improved product quality and various other benefits.

¹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/unlock-cei/>

Figure 2: Business outcomes expected from IoT projects (source: UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)

Yet the IoT market is still in an early phase of development. Companies have long struggled to complete IoT projects and scale them across their organizations due to high complexity, security concerns, high costs, project delays, and lack of key skills. As shown by the aforementioned survey, only 16% of respondents claimed their IoT projects were very successful, though 45% claimed they were somewhat successful². Companies are experiencing some benefits from IoT, but not necessarily as great or as easily achieved as hoped.

A key reason companies have not had greater success with IoT projects until now is that the advanced use cases are still in development. Many early IoT use cases are relatively simple, such as sending utility meter data from smart meters or tracking vehicles with fleet management systems. In the longer term, combining IoT data with advanced analytics, distributed edge computing, AI, and automation can transform companies and industries. However, the technologies and use cases that will enable this transformation are still in development.

3.2 AI and analytics in IoT

Analytics play a crucial role on the IoT by transforming the vast amounts of data generated by connected devices into actionable insights and automated systems. These insights help in understanding patterns, trends, and anomalies, which can inform decision-making and strategic planning. Beyond the insights, the real power of IoT analytics often lies in its ability to automate actions based on the insights gained. This means that instead of just providing information, the system can automatically make adjustments or trigger actions without human intervention. For example, a system might enable predictive maintenance, whereby the system might detect a problem and automatically schedule maintenance.

There are four main types of data analytics:

- **Descriptive Analytics:** This type describes what happened by summarizing past data.
- **Diagnostic Analytics:** Explains why something happened by identifying patterns and relationships in the data.
- **Predictive Analytics:** This type forecasts what is likely to happen in the future based on historical data.

² Source: UNLOCK CEI Survey, March 2023, and D1.2 of UNLOCK-CEI project

- **Prescriptive Analytics:** It provides recommendations on how to act by using data to determine the best course of action.

According to IDC³, and based on a survey of European enterprises using IoT, the largest shares of respondents claimed they were using diagnostic (29.7%) and predictive analytics (28.5%) for their IoT projects, with a smaller share using more advanced prescriptive analytics (14.7%), and another significant share using simpler descriptive analytics (16.4%).

n = 848 (Europe, respondents using IoT)

Figure 3: IoT Analytics Stage of Development (source: IDC Europe 5G and IoT Survey, August 2024)

Artificial Intelligence can play a key role in all the stages of IoT analytics. For example:

- In descriptive analytics, AI-driven models may be critical for computer vision to identify the identity of people in an area, to read vehicle license plates, or to enable quality control to identify production defects.
- In diagnostic analytics, AI plays a more significant role by using machine learning algorithms to identify patterns and correlations in the data. This helps in understanding the reasons behind past events.
- Predictive analytics relies heavily on AI. Machine learning models analyze historical data to predict future outcomes. Techniques such as regression analysis, classification, and clustering are commonly used to forecast trends and behaviors.
- In prescriptive analytics, AI is crucial. It not only predicts future outcomes but also suggests actions to achieve desired results. Advanced AI techniques, including optimisation algorithms and reinforcement learning, are used to recommend the best course of action.

Using analytics in IoT comes with several significant challenges. Many of these challenges relate to managing data, models, and infrastructure. Among the challenges are:

- **Data Challenges**

³ Source: IDC's European 5G and IoT Survey, August 2024

- **Data Volume and Velocity:** Managing and processing the massive amounts of data generated by IoT devices in real-time.
- **Data Quality:** Ensuring the data is clean, complete, and consistent for accurate analytics.
- **Heterogeneous Data Sources:** Integrating and standardising data from diverse sources and formats.
- **Security and Privacy:** Protecting sensitive data and ensuring privacy in IoT environments.
- **Model Challenges**
 - **Training Models:** Handling the resource-intensive process of training machine learning models on large datasets.
 - **Model Lifecycle Management:** Managing the deployment, monitoring, updating, and retraining of models to keep them effective over time.
 - **Managing Large Numbers of Models:** Orchestrating and coordinating numerous models across various devices and locations.
- **Infrastructure Challenges**
 - **Scalability:** Scaling systems to handle increasing data loads and numbers of devices.
 - **Distributed Edge Computing:** Managing distributed computing infrastructure and analytics models at the edge and in the cloud.
 - **Real-time Processing:** Achieving low-latency processing for timely insights and actions.
 - **Long-term Maintenance:** Managing software updates, hardware replacements, and overall system upkeep.

IDC's survey highlighted how significant these challenges are. European enterprise IoT users were asked about the most challenging steps in their IoT projects, and the top choice was managing the data, such as collecting the data, cleaning it, securing it and disposing of it (see figure 4). Companies struggle with data from the outset and must make significant decisions about their IoT solution design in order to overcome these data challenges.

n = 950 (Europe, all respondents)
Source:

Figure 4: Most challenging steps in IoT projects (source: European 5G IoT Survey, August 2024)

When looking more closely at IoT analytics, respondents identified a range of challenges. After overall costs, the top challenges cited were preparing the data, deploying ML models to heterogeneous end points, and capturing data reliably (see figure 5)

n = 812 (Europe, using IoT analytics in any stage)

Figure 5: Top challenges in IoT Analytics (source: European 5G IoT Survey, August 2024)

PANDORA aims to directly address some of these challenges and make AIoT analytics more feasible. In particular, the project is addressing the problem of scarce data with solutions to develop synthetic data that can overcome insufficient volumes of data for model training, thus aligning with clear market needs.

3.3 Edge computing and IoT

IoT use cases can produce large amounts of data at the edge of the network. Some local edge computing resources may be needed just to manage, filter and clean the data at the edge, before sending it to the cloud. However, with larger and more advanced use cases, organizations may need to deploy extensive edge infrastructure to handle the larger volume of devices and data, to reduce costs of cloud storage and network traffic, and to put the computing resources closer to the end devices to provide higher reliability and lower latency, especially in the cases of automated systems.

Use of edge computing lags the adoption of IoT. As seen below, only 6% of respondents were using edge extensively at the time of the survey (March 2023). Manufacturers were slightly ahead of the average company, with 9% then using extensively. Still, edge adoption is in its early stages. Edge adoption is less mature, in part because it is most needed for more advanced solutions, many of which are still in development and not yet widely deployed.

Figure 6: Edge Usage and Plans by Industry

Though edge usage is modest thus far, most companies expect they will need edge in their future IoT projects. A recent survey of European enterprise IoT users showed that 83.8% of respondents expect to use a combination of cloud and edge computing in their future IoT projects (see figure 7). That same survey showed that these companies expected to use edge computing in a variety of locations, including on the telco network edge, on premises, and on the device.

n = 942 (Europe, Using or planning to use IoT)

Figure 7: Usage of Edge and Cloud Computing in IoT projects (source: European 5G IoT Survey, August 2024)

Companies expect to use edge for several reasons. The most common reason mentioned is that it improves security, because data is not travelling across the network and out to a distant cloud or data center. The next most popular reason is that it reduces data volumes sent across the network, followed by overcoming unreliable connectivity.

n=500 (Base: Edge users or planners)

Figure 8: Benefits of Edge Computing (source: UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)

Yet edge computing deployment and management remain challenging. The survey showed there is reluctance to use edge for several reasons. Costs and security were the top concerns, followed closely by lack of adequate IT infrastructure and skills (as reflected in figure 9).

n=700 (Base: all respondents)

Figure 9: Edge Challenges (source: UNLOCK-CEI Survey, March 2023)

Other challenges needed by the industry to address for edge adoption to reach its potential⁴ are:

- Edge software solutions are too complex and fragmented.
- There are many incompatible proprietary platforms.
- There is a need for more open-source edge platforms and open standards.
- Organizations are not ready for the needed edge data management and governance.

⁴ Source: UNLOCK CEI, D1.3, Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape: CEI Gap Analysis and Opportunities

- There are too many incompatible OT protocols.
- There is a need for a common language and taxonomy/ontology around edge solutions.
- There is a need for solutions to aid the development of device-edge applications.

3.4 AIoT and Sustainability

Sustainability aspects are becoming increasingly important in decisions taken by companies about technology adoption. The graphics below, based on IDC market data from 2024, give a hint on where companies were (2023 vs 2024) in terms of status of adoption of IoT solutions for sustainability (showing the level of maturity of such deployments) as well as how important sustainability is in the decision-making process around IoT.

Figure 10: IoT solutions and sustainability (source: IDC Europe 5G and IoT Survey, August 2024)

Figure 11: Importance of sustainability in IoT decision-making (source: IDC Europe 5G and IoT Survey, August 2024)

4. PANDORA Plans & Operations

4.1 Exploitation and adoption of PANDORA results

The success of PANDORA project as a whole depends on the consortium's coordinated efforts and ability to overcome the challenges related to bringing trustworthy datasets to the market.

PANDORA participates in the vast and growing market of Artificial Intelligence that is currently valued⁵ at **USD 184.04 billion**, expecting to reach **USD 826.73 billion in 2030**. The major drivers for the market are the increasing number of large and complex datasets, unavailability of real datasets, evolving Industrial IoT and automation, and improving computing power. Untrustworthy AI technologies could negatively impact economic growth and emphasize the need to address the AI risks for any AI-enabled solutions.

4.1.1 Objectives for exploitation

The primary objectives for the exploitation of PANDORA are to address challenges related to trustworthy datasets and to bring the project's outcomes to the market. The specific objectives include:

- **Commercialisation:** To bring innovative AIoT-enabled applications to the market, addressing the need for trustworthy training datasets and reliable AIoT services.
- **Standardisation:** To contribute to the development of standards for AIoT systems, particularly focusing on data quality, transparency, fairness, safety, and robustness as per the European Commission's AI Act.
- **Education and Training:** To enhance the skills and knowledge of stakeholders through training programs, workshops, and educational materials, facilitating the effective adoption of PANDORA's technologies.

4.1.2 Methodological approach

The exploitation strategy for PANDORA follows the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) methodology, ensuring a structured and iterative process:

- **Plan:** Develop a detailed exploitation plan, including market analysis, target group identification, and a go-to-market strategy. Define key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of exploitation activities.
- **Do:** Implement the exploitation activities, such as market introduction, pilot projects, and collaborations. Conduct outreach and dissemination via open and transparent practices, including events and dissemination channels.
- **Check:** Monitor and evaluate the progress of exploitation activities, gathering feedback from stakeholders and measuring against KPIs. Conduct regular reviews to assess the effectiveness of the exploitation strategy.
- **Act:** Refine and improve exploitation strategies based on feedback and evaluation results. Update the exploitation plan to address any identified gaps or opportunities for improvement.

⁵ Artificial intelligence (AI) market size worldwide from 2020 to 2030, <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1474143/global-ai-market-size> (needs proper citation)

Figure 12: Exploitation methodology

4.1.3 Preliminary definition of PANDORA exploitable results

The following list summarizes the main areas of exploitable results, followed by the Unique Selling Points of PANDORA as defined at the initial stage of the project. This information is complemented by the exercise run by partners to identify in concrete terms the expected KER, with details for them, when available.

- **Trustworthy Training Datasets:** Development of advanced techniques for synthetic data generation, uncertainty quantification, and data summarization to provide reliable training datasets for AIoT-enabled applications.
- **AlaaS and CaaS Architectures:** Novel AI as a Service (AlaaS) and Computation as a Service (CaaS) architectures that ensure robust, explainable, and green operation of AIoT applications.
- **Explainable AI and Domain-Informed Models:** Implementation of explainable AI and domain-informed model training/testing to enhance trust and performance in AIoT applications.
- **Pilot Case Studies:** Real-world validation of the PANDORA framework through pilot cases in smart buildings, factories, and critical infrastructures.

Unique Selling Propositions (USP)

- **Trustworthiness:** PANDORA ensures high-quality, reliable training datasets essential for effective AIoT-enabled applications.
- **Efficiency and Sustainability:** The framework promotes green AIoT applications, reducing environmental impact.
- **Explainability:** The use of explainable AI techniques increases transparency and trust in AIoT-enabled applications.
- **Real-world Validation:** Successful pilot cases demonstrate the practical applicability and benefits of the PANDORA framework.

Preliminary identification of Key Exploitable Results (KER)

The following table presents all the KERs that have been identified at the time of submitting this report. Details on each of them are provided later on through individual KER fiches. This

information (both details on exploitable assets and the full identification of them) will evolve throughout the course of the project and will be appropriately documented.

Table 1: List of KER (Key Exploitable Results)

No	Title	Owner
1	Synthetic data generation	IMT
2	Uncertainty quantification modelling and development	DLR
3	Domain-Informed Data Analysis for Explainable AI	UNIBO
4	Automated Data Labeling and Annotation	UNSPMF
5	Data Summarization, Dimensionality Reduction, and Fusion	ITML
6	Verification and Validation	Framatome
7	Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence	UNSPMF
8	Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning	CYU/ENSEA
9	Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations	UNSPMF-FRL
10	Hybrid Learning-Reasoning Approach for Model Explainability	Framatome
11	Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models	AU
12	Adaptive distribution and optimisation of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing continuum	AU
13	User Authentication Component	CBRL

KER #1 - Synthetic data generation

Partner: IMT	KER # 1 - Synthetic data generation
Brief description	Synthetic Data Generation for AIoT applications that create realistic simulated IoT data representing normal operations and anomalous conditions.
Innovation capacity	Generates IoT data under diverse situations and scenarios, producing balanced datasets that enhance AI model training and testing.
Market trends	Growing demand for synthetic data solutions as organizations face data scarcity and privacy constraints in IoT development.
Competitors	State-of-the-art approaches for data generation from AI startups, academic researchers, and established technology companies.
Target audiences	Groups building AIoT applications, including industrial automation companies, smart infrastructure developers, and IoT platform vendors.

KER # 2 – Uncertainty quantification modelling and development

Partner: DLR	KER # 2 – Uncertainty quantification modelling and development
Brief description	Uncertainty quantification modelling leverages methods from Bayesian and ensemble approaches to identify and measure uncertainties coming from the data and models. Bayesian methods update beliefs based on new data, while ensemble techniques run multiple models to capture a range of possible outcomes. The human-in-the-loop concept integrates expert judgement to further refine and interpret results, enhancing model accuracy and decision-making in complex situations. This helps assess reliability, minimise false positives, and improve anomaly detection.
Innovation capacity	This component innovates by developing hybrid methods that disentangle epistemic (knowledge-based) and aleatoric (data-driven) uncertainties. By adding a human-in-the-loop approach, it combines computational models with expert input to improve uncertainty quantification and model accuracy. This can help provide more robust decision-making while enhancing trustworthiness in predictive AI models through reliable confidence scores.
Market trends	Uncertainty quantification is a growing field focused on understanding and measuring the uncertainty in models and predictions used in various domains (engineering, physics, energy, finance, automobile and more). As technology becomes more complex, it's important to know how much confidence we can have in the results from these machine learning models. Methods for quantifying uncertainties help to estimate and manage the uncertainties, making predictions more reliable. With the rise of new tools like machine learning and advanced simulations, the ability to analyse uncertainty is improving. This trend is expected to keep growing as more industries look for better ways to manage risks and make more accurate decisions in real-time scenarios, with increasing demand for interpretable AI in sensitive infrastructure safety systems.
Competitors	Competitors in the uncertainty quantification modelling and development include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • simulation and engineering software companies, which integrate these methods into their design and simulation platforms • specialized firms that focus on uncertainty quantification tools for risk analysis, reliability, and optimisation. • research labs that contribute to advanced UQ methodologies for high-performance computing applications • sensitive infrastructure enterprises
Target audiences	Industries, academia, operators of hydrogen refueling stations, predictive maintenance solution providers, and regulatory bodies prioritising safety.

KER # 3 – Domain-Informed Data Analysis for Explainable AI

Partner: UNIBO	KER # 3 – Domain-Informed Data Analysis for Explainable AI
Brief description	Incorporate domain-informed data analysis to derive insights about data generation and causal relationships, enhancing explainability of AI outputs.
Innovation capacity	Supports explainable AI for safety-critical applications, fostering trust and transparency for decision-makers in hydrogen infrastructure.
Market trends	High demand for explainable AI solutions in industrial settings to comply with regulatory standards and user trust requirements.
Competitors	Under analysis
Target audiences	Energy and hydrogen refueling station operators, regulatory agencies, and AI solution developers focused on energy infrastructure.

KER # 4 – Automated Data Labeling and Annotation

Partner: UNSPMF	KER # 4 – Semi-automated annotations, labelling and self-supervised completion and augmentation (DACL)
Brief description	Data completeness is one of the most important dataset quality attributes, especially when machine learning methods expect data points without missing values for input and target variables, and when it is desirable to have class balance. DACL methods and corresponding software modules perform missing value inference, missing label inference, and data augmentation in order to form complete and balanced trustworthy datasets for training predictive models for AIoT operations. DACL possesses internal quality control mechanisms realized by hybrid outlier detection methods. This automation of data labeling and annotation improves training data quality, enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of anomaly detection models.
Innovation capacity	The main innovations of DACL are the following: (1) missing value inference based on transfer learning, (2) missing label inference based on graph learning algorithms and graph-based models, (3) quality control by anomaly detection based on unsupervised hybrid models involving different machine learning designs, (4) data augmentation by novel oversampling techniques taking into account local intrinsic dimensionality and hubness properties of data points. These innovations accelerate model training cycles and reduce manual effort, leading to faster, high quality anomaly detection tailored for hydrogen station safety.
Market trends	The market for data annotation, labeling, completion, and augmentation is rapidly growing, driven by the increasing demand for complete datasets in machine and deep learning. It is evident that we live in the era of big data required by contemporary AI methods. However, due to complex data collection, acquisition and aggregation procedures that are prone to various kinds of errors, human involvement in large-scale data annotation and labeling and complex data models, resulting datasets are almost always incomplete and inaccurate to a certain degree. There is growing use of automated data annotation in industrial AI applications to reduce costs and enhance data reliability.
Competitors	Academy (ML/DL researchers), research and development AI industry and startups, providers of AI data management and automation tools, particularly those serving the energy and predictive maintenance sectors.

Target audiences	Academy, AIoT industry and startups, AI model developers, hydrogen refueling station operators, and data annotation solution providers.
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KER # 5 – Data Summarisation, Dimensionality Reduction, and Fusion

Partner: ITML	KER # 5 – Data Summarisation, Dimensionality Reduction, and Fusion
Brief description	By reducing data dimensions and complexity, this component ensures that only the most important features of the data are preserved. Its main goal is to offer advanced functionality for dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction across various types of raw data (images, videos, time series, multimodal inputs, etc.) to reduce the computational load of subsequent processing tasks. Additionally, it provides metrics quantifying the extent of reduction and complexity, while streamlining data for anomaly detection by focusing on relevant patterns and reducing data redundancy.
Innovation capacity	The innovation capacity lies in the combination of feature analysis and extraction methods with interpretability, multimodal data handling, and transformation into semantically rich data forms. This integration of explainability, modularity, and quantifiable metrics sets it apart, offering efficiency, accuracy, and transparency in data processing. Its applicability across diverse fields—from AI-enabled systems and IoT to critical infrastructure—enhances its impact potential, giving it a wide range of applications in scalable, performance-intensive environments. This component also provides significant data quality enhancement.
Market trends	The market for dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and data simplification tools is rapidly growing, driven by the increasing demand for efficient data processing in AI, machine learning, and big data analytics. As organizations handle massive volumes of multimodal data from sources like IoT, social media, and complex enterprise systems, tools that streamline data complexity are crucial. There is a strong focus on integrating explainable dimensionality reduction methods, with industries like finance, healthcare, and cybersecurity leading adoption due to data complexity, transparency, and regulatory needs. Additionally, scalable, modular solutions that support diverse data types and ensure easy integration via APIs are becoming standard. This trend is underscored by the rise in containerized, cloud-ready architectures and increased adoption of data reduction techniques in real-time AI applications to manage large data volumes and improve performance.
Competitors	Big tech companies; startups focusing on AI; innovative methodologies by academia; and companies offering specialised data processing and fusion techniques tailored for predictive maintenance and safety applications.
Target audiences	Energy sector AI developers, hydrogen station operators, and companies in need of efficient data management solutions

KER # 6 – Verification and Validation

Partner: Framatome	KER # 6 – Verification and Validation
Brief description	Implement verification and validation to ensure reliable and accurate anomaly detection under varied operational conditions, confirming true positives.
Innovation capacity	Supports continuous monitoring and validation of AI models, enhancing robustness for safety-critical environments in hydrogen refueling stations.

Market trends	Growing need for reliable AI validation in predictive maintenance, especially within the evolving hydrogen fuel sector.
Competitors	Under analysis
Target audiences	Under analysis

KER # 7 – Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence

Partner: UNSPMF	KER # 7 – Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence (CRV)
Brief description	This software component enables dynamic and robust model adaptation through several key features: it incorporates novelty detection to identify new patterns in incoming training data, supports incremental class learning to handle new classes as they emerge, and allows for continuous model augmentation. The inference engine facilitates efficient deployment of trained models, while a cross-model validation mechanism leverages high-precision, high-recall combinations to enhance predictive performance across models. This component is optimised for use in adaptive machine learning systems where real-time adjustments and scalable accuracy are crucial. These capabilities can be applied to predict failures and anomalies proactively, enabling preemptive action for component failures at hydrogen refueling stations.
Innovation capacity	The main innovations of CRV are: (1) cross-model validation for continuous learning models using the high-precision high-recall model combination for self-validating its performance (2) novelty detection and separation (3) incremental class learning. These innovations add a proactive layer to maintenance, supporting continuous availability and high safety standards for hydrogen stations.
Market trends	The market for flexible and performant continuous learning models is growing day by day. While various modern techniques for developing models evolve, task-oriented applications of models are increasing at an even faster rate. Various methodologies so far do work where pre-trained models have satisfied the needs of the market so far, they don't saturate the requirements of flexibility in learning, augmenting and performance validation of models which receive novel data for continuous learning. There is also a surge in AI-driven failure prediction for infrastructure safety and an increasing demand for reliable AI in clean energy applications.
Competitors	Academia (ML/DL researchers), research and development AI industry and startups, competitors in predictive maintenance focused on critical infrastructure, especially in energy sectors.
Target audiences	Academia, AIoT industry and startups, hydrogen fuel providers, predictive maintenance solution vendors, and regulators in the clean energy domain.

KER #8 - Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning

Partner: CYU/ENSEA	KER 8 - Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning
Brief description	Explainability for outputs of diagnostic and predictive maintenance machine learning models.

Innovation capacity	Even though there has been a vivid interest in the domain of Explainable AI (XAI) in the last few years, exploring XAI for Predictive Maintenance and other continuous data-based applications is a promising field.
Market trends	Explainability for Machine Learning outputs in critical environments are gaining importance and are more and more required by experts and users in different domains as IoT management, predictive maintenance for industrial machines, etc. Moreover, due to recent laws for transparency in AI, explainability has been established as a requirement in the applications manipulating personal data.
Competitors	State of the art algorithms for explainability of Machine Learning results applied over continuous data.
Target audiences	Industries/Companies that employ Machine Learning and need explainable results; Academia for Research and Teaching

KER # 9 – Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations

Partner: UNSPMF-FRL	KER # 9 – Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations
Brief description	FRL is the combination of federated learning techniques with representational learning. The aim is learning compact data representations of input data in a federated setting, thus reducing the complexity of the domain data, and using these latent representations for specific learning tasks. Representational learning has been shown to increase the performance of ML models in multi-task learning. Since clients in FL environments may have significantly different data distributions between them, the FL task is similar in nature to multi-task learning. By introducing representational learning to FL settings, the robustness of ML models can be increased.
Innovation capacity	FRL is still a relatively fresh area of interest with multiple research directions available. Effort has already been taken to bring representational learning to federated environments, however, research gaps which fit PANDORA’s use cases can be identified: (1) training effective inference models from representations obtained through FL; (2) the use of FRL in outlier detection can be improved through the development of novel aggregation functions suitable for attention-based FRL models.
Market trends	FL has been applied to numerous different use cases spanning many different domains, for example IoT and medicine. This distributed learning paradigm offers advantages like increased privacy, reduced communication and computational costs, and eliminates the need for data centralisation. Because of this it can benefit numerous distributed learning scenarios. The use cases in IoT are clear, data collection is carried out by numerous different IoT edge devices, consequently data centralisation isn’t preferred as it introduces communication overhead, challenges with data storage, and delayed learning. By learning directly at the edge, these problems are mitigated. Combining FL with learning representations (FRL) leads to increased robustness of the global models obtained through this learning paradigm, as learning abstract representations of input data can help models generalize better over the entire pool of edge devices. Organizations handling massive amounts of data being collected by many different edge devices can benefit greatly by introducing FRL to their data pipelines and shifting the learning process to the edge. Research efforts on the topic of FL and

	FLR from both academia and industry are still steadily increasing, which is evident from the number of published research articles.
Competitors	Academy Researches (AI/ML), R&D Startups in the AI industry
Target audiences	Academy, IoT

KER # 10 Hybrid Learning-Reasoning Approach for Model Explainability

Partner: Framatome	KER # 10 Hybrid Learning-Reasoning Approach for Model Explainability
Brief description	Use hybrid learning-reasoning methods to make model outputs explainable, aiding causal analysis and supporting better decision-making.
Innovation capacity	Facilitates clear, actionable insights from model predictions, enhancing trust and decision-making for anomaly prevention.
Market trends	Demand for hybrid AI systems that combine reasoning with learning, especially in safety-oriented industries.
Competitors	Under analysis
Target audiences	Operators of hydrogen refueling stations, AI developers focused on explainability, and stakeholders prioritizing safe AI applications.

KER # 11 – Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models

Partner: AU	KER # 11 – Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models
Brief description	This KER will focus on methodologies for developing Continual Inference Networks for improving efficiency in classification tasks defined on sequence data (visual and/or multi-dimensional time-series). The methodologies will be published in scientific publication venues (journals and/or conferences) and the prototype implementations will be made publicly available in code repositories (e.g., GitHub, GitLab). A component implementing one of these methodologies will be developed to be used in the Use Cases showcasing the functionality. The methodology selection will be based on various criteria, including effectiveness, efficiency, and robustness.
Innovation capacity	The KER targets new methodological contributions in sequence data processing by Continual Inference Networks. Methodological innovations are the main target of this KER.
Market trends	Efficient processing of sequence data is an active research topic. Developed approaches follow different directions, including lightweight Deep Learning models, and models designed for sequence data processing. This KER will exploit the most promising existing approaches for developing competitive models against the existing solutions.
Competitors	Academic Institutions with research focus on Machine Learning, Computer Vision, Data Analytics. Research & Development of companies focused on data intensive application areas.

Target audiences	Academic Institutions with research focus on Machine Learning, Computer Vision, Data Analytics. Research & Development of companies focused on data intensive application areas.
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KER # 12 – Adaptive distribution and optimisation of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing continuum

Partner: AU	KER # 11 – Adaptive distribution and optimisation of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing continuum
Brief description	This KER will focus on methodologies for developing Deep Learning models suitable for Distributed Inference for the Cloud-Edge Computing Continuum. The methodologies will be published in scientific publication venues (journals and/or conferences) and the prototype implementations will be made publicly available in code repositories (e.g., GitHub, GitLab).
Innovation capacity	The KER targets new methodological contributions in Distributed Inference for Neural Networks.
Market trends	Distributed Inference and optimisation of AI models is an active research topic. Developed approaches try to determine neural network architectures suitable for distributing their calculations in different processing devices while also considering the capabilities of the communication channel for transmitting data/information between the devices during inference. This KER will exploit the most promising existing approaches for developing competitive models against the existing solutions.
Competitors	Academic Institutions with research focus on the intersection between AI and Communications.
Target audiences	Academic Institutions with research focus on the intersection between AI and Communications. Research & Development of companies with applications involving decentralized/edge decision making by AI.

KER # 13 – User Authentication Component (UAC)

Partner: CBRL	KER # 12 – User Authentication Component (UAC)
Brief description	The User Authentication Component (UAC) integrates Keycloak to provide secure user authentication through the User Interface, managing the login/logout flow and session handling. It issues tokens for authenticated access to system resources, processing validation requests from the UI and Intent Manager components for secure, controlled access within PANDORA.
Innovation capacity	The UAC builds on Keycloak’s established architecture rather than introducing new technology. Its primary innovation lies in its integration with PANDORA’s specific components (UI and Intent Manager), creating a secure authentication flow essential for access control within the system.
Market trends	The demand for reliable authentication systems in AI and IoT is driven by increasing data privacy regulations and a need for scalable, secure access control across platforms. Token-based authentication is becoming a standard practice in distributed systems.

Competitors	Keycloak competes with established identity and access management solutions like Okta, and AWS Cognito, which offer similar secure access features for complex environments.
Target audiences	Organizations working with AI/IoT solutions that require secure, scalable user authentication, enterprises in need of centralized security management, and developers focused on integrating security into distributed architectures.

4.1.4 Operational Plan for the exploitation of PANDORA

Phase 1: Pilot Deployment and Testing (Year 1-2)

We need to verify PANDORA's solutions at the first pilot locations in high-stakes industries (energy, smart buildings, and manufacturing). Within each pilot setting, specific objectives include energy monitoring, safety improvement, and failure prediction.

P1.1 Conduct feasibility studies

We will begin by determining whether deploying PANDORA's AI services in the chosen trial sites is technically, financially, and operationally feasible. This entails examining the data that is available, the infrastructure needs, and any current systems that the new AIoT applications need to interface with.

P1.2 Deploy initial AI models

AI models for failure prediction, safety monitoring, and energy optimisation need to be put into practice. We will begin with a limited number of devices or operational units in order to control the scope and lower the first risks.

P1.3 Gather performance data

To evaluate the efficacy of the system, we will gather operational data in real time from sensors, devices, and AI models during the initial deployment phase. We will focus on crucial performance metrics such as safety event reduction, energy savings, and prediction accuracy.

P1.4 Analyze outcomes against control groups to ensure scalability

We will establish control groups that do not use AI-based solutions to compare performance. This will help determine the impact of the AI system and validate its effectiveness.

Phase 2: Optimisation and Scaling (Year 2-3)

Our objective on Phase 2 is to refine predictive models based on pilot outcomes in order to enhance synthetic data generation and improve edge AI models to maximize their accuracy and operational efficiency.

P2.1 Integrate feedback loops from pilot testing

We will gather insights from pilot site operators, maintenance teams, and other stakeholders to understand the strengths and weaknesses of the deployed AIoT applications. We will incorporate this feedback to make iterative improvements to the models and systems.

P2.2 Optimise synthetic data for quality assurance

Where real-world data is limited, PANDORA will generate synthetic data to enhance model training, testing and deployment. We will focus on generating diverse, high-quality datasets to simulate edge cases, rare failure events, or other hard-to-capture scenarios

P2.3 Adapt solutions for larger-scale deployments

We will prepare the AIoT applications for wider implementation by adapting them to handle increased data volume, more complex operational environments, and diverse use cases across various industries.

Phase 3: Market Launch and Adoption (Year 3)

Our objective on Phase 3 is to transition validated solutions into broader market applications, establishing PANDORA as a leading solution in predictive maintenance, safety compliance, and infrastructure monitoring.

P3.1 Launch product offerings with partner endorsement

We will officially launch PANDORA's AaaS and CaaS solutions to the broader market, leveraging the positive results from pilot projects as proof points. We will use endorsements from pilot partners like Siemens and Philips to demonstrate the value and reliability of the system.

P3.2 Conduct targeted marketing

We will implement targeted marketing campaigns aimed at industries with the highest demand for AIoT application deployment. We suggest using industry conferences, webinars, and digital marketing to raise awareness of PANDORA's products.

P3.3 Initiate large-scale training programs to support client adoption

Finally, we will launch training programs for end-users in order to support client adoption. These include detailed onboarding sessions, user manuals, and online tutorials to ensure that users can fully integrate PANDORA's services into their operations.

4.1.5 Exploitation interests per category of partners

Academic & Research Org (NTUA, AU, IMT, STUBA, CY, UNIBO, DLR, TUM, UNSPMF, IISC, UOFT): They will exploit the outcomes of PANDORA for the re-utilisation of the research and technological know-how acquired for future research activities and services. They will also seek to create additional teaching material for both graduate and postgraduate courses relating to data analytics and big data. Finally, they will explore exploitation opportunities including: i) Transferring results and know-how into further EU, national, industrial, and international projects, ii) Developing new services based on the prototypes and tools.

Technology Partners (AEGIS, CBRL, SLC, ITML, DIE, EUNL): They will use the PANDORA outcomes for strengthening their services and product portfolio. This will be possible by enhancing current products or creating new services to support their client base. Using the knowledge gained in the project, business partners will have the opportunity to create synergies, demonstrate their technological offerings and increase their business capacity.

Industrial Providers (EAB, SAG, PCL, IDC, HALCOR, THALES): These organizations will participate in the project by executing the use cases and relevant validation and cross-validation activities. Through the adoption of the PANDORA results, these institutions will immediately uptake the results in optimising the accuracy and effectiveness of IoT enhanced environments with AIoT applications, while gaining hands-on experience with trustworthy data sets and technologies for their technical experts and professionals.

4.2 Dissemination, Marketing and Communications

4.2.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

This chapter describes the dissemination and communication strategy followed for the PANDORA project. First, there is an overview of the overall strategy, then the different target audiences are described. Additionally, it integrates the project partners' dissemination and communication plans.

Overview of the Dissemination and Communication Approach

The dissemination and communication strategy is described in this section, along with methods for effectively informing stakeholders regarding the project's progress and results. A variety of conventional and online media is used to maximize exposure and engagement. Key tools include an up-to-date website, active social media presence (LinkedIn, X, YouTube), newsletters, press releases, and traditional presentation materials. The following sections emphasize target audiences that have significant impact in their respective disciplines, such as the scientific and industrial sectors. Additionally, the strategy includes focused actions to promote face-to-face communication with key stakeholders.

Objectives of Dissemination and Communication. The aim of the PANDORA dissemination and communication strategy will be to make sure that each project outcome reaches the desired target effectively, through an appropriate channel at the best time possible. In detail:

- **Raising Awareness:** To create awareness of the project's objectives, progress, and outcomes within the target audience, fostering an understanding of its aims and value.
- **Engaging Stakeholders** To engage the stakeholders and involve them in such a way that they would support and show interest in the project initiatives.
- **Establishing a strong project identity:** Promote and reinforce a distinct identity matching PANDORA's vision and values to enhance recognition and coherence.
- **Facilitating Knowledge Transfer:** To ensure that the knowledge and insights generated by the project are effectively transferred to the target audience, with an emphasis on accessibility and practical application.
- **Increasing Visibility:** This would enhance the visibility and public profile of the project both within relevant communities and the general public, each with significant reach and impact.
- **Fostering Collaboration:** The purpose of this is to collaborate towards an exchange of information and resources, ensuring the greatest possible impact and sustainability of the project's results. The collective sum of these objectives is to ensure that PANDORA influence is increased, that stakeholder engagement is purposeful and to help effectively disseminate the knowledge and resources that are developed within the project's life cycle.

Target Groups and Audience

The dissemination and communication activities of the PANDORA project will be directed to a wide range of target groups with the objective of enhancing the impact and uptake of the project deliverables. The main targets would include:

- **European Research & Development Communities:** This would include all researchers or academic institutions involved in data science, artificial intelligence, and applied sciences. This would include users in general who are supposed to extend the basic advances that PANDORA will make in data discovery, trustworthy AI model development, and real-time data processing for further research and the development of related educational content.
- **Small and Medium Enterprises-SMEs:** PANDORA will seek to support various industry SMEs in facilitating the methods and tools to extract actionable knowledge from

proprietary datasets. Project outputs aim at providing such organizations with means to inject reliable AI-driven insights throughout operations.

- **Technology Providers:** Technology providers into AI and IoT are key beneficiaries of PANDORA's work as they will enhance their product offerings and services through the integration of trustworthy data and intelligent data pipelines. The project outputs provide a basis for technology providers to innovate in AIoT applications.
- **Regulatory Bodies and Policymakers:** Interaction with regulatory bodies and policy makers is of vital importance because it provides the basis for standards in applications of AI and building trust in them. The contributions of PANDORA to robust, transparent models of AI underpin these bodies in their development of policies to enable ethical AI adoption and sustainable data use within the EU and internationally.
- **Public Sector & Policy Initiatives:** By promoting open data sharing and collaborative data value chains, PANDORA contributes to the EU's vision for a competitive and high-performing data economy. Collaboration with European Data Spaces is a key element in aligning PANDORA's developments with larger EU digital strategies.
- **Public & Industrial Stakeholders:** Activities of public engagement are run with appropriate open-access workshops, training sessions, and online resources for informing and engaging industry stakeholders and the wider public. These will undertake trust-building in AI technology, user education on data privacy, and spread best practices for ethical AI across industry.

4.2.2 Individual Dissemination and Communication Plans

Table 2: Individual dissemination Plans for PANDORA

No	Partner	Area	Dissemination Plan
1	NTUA	Coordination – Academic & Research	<p>NTUA's dissemination plan incorporates a comprehensive set of activities aimed at enhancing the outreach of the University and its associated research groups within their respective fields, including Computer Vision, Machine Learning (ML), and Software Engineering. The targeted dissemination will involve publishing scientific articles in high-impact journals such as the International Journal of Computer Vision, Future Generation Computer Systems, IEEE Internet of Things Journal, and IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing.</p> <p>Additionally, NTUA plans to engage with the scientific community by presenting research at prominent conferences and contributing to their proceedings. These include the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), the Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), the European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV), IEEE Cloud, and the IEEE International Conference on Big Data Computing Service and Machine Learning Applications.</p> <p>NTUA will also organize or participate in workshops and tutorials at leading conferences to showcase research and provide hands-on training. Additionally, the participating teams will release software libraries, tools, and datasets developed as part of the project under open-source licenses. At the same time, NTUA will leverage its resources to contribute to community-based open-source projects related to the project's topics. This will facilitate engagement with other members of</p>

			the community and increase NTUA's visibility within these networks.
2	AU	Academic & Research	AU plans to disseminate research results via publications in international journals and conferences, and presentations of research outcomes in the corresponding venues. Research results of AU will be integrated in research-focused teaching and project activities as state-of-the-art approaches. AU has already organized a Special Session at the IEEE MLSP 2024 in collaboration with the Nordic University Cooperation on Edge Intelligence (NUEI) funded by the NordForsk foundation in which it is a partner organization and could contribute to the organization of similar Special Session/Issue activities of the consortium.
3	EAB	Industrial Provider	EAB plans to publish research results, as an outcome of Pandora, to international conferences and journals. In addition, the use cases can be submitted with the demonstration track of various venues to showcase the efficacy of approaches. Within EAB, we will highlight the outcomes of Pandora so that the research results can be incorporated into our products and customer solutions.
4	IMT	Academic & Research	IMT plans to disseminate research results via publications in international conferences and journals, and presentations of research outcomes in the corresponding venues. Research results of IMT will be integrated in research-focused teaching and project activities as state-of-the-art approaches. IMT plans to participate in the organization of Special Sessions in well know venues, as well as Special Session/Issue activities of the consortium.
5	SAG	Industrial Provider	SAG plans to publish developed research results in important conferences and journals. For projects visibility, SAG will participate in BDVA organized events following i3-MARKET approach.
6	AEGIS	Technology Provider	AEGIS is planning to disseminate the key results and outcomes of the PANDORA project through various established business and research channels. These include participation in EU research and development (R&D) workshops, where findings will be shared with leading experts and stakeholders to foster collaborative discussion and knowledge exchange. Additionally, AEGIS will present at prominent international conferences, specifically targeting events focused on AIoT and related technologies. This strategy aims to engage with a broad spectrum of academic, industrial, and governmental audiences to maximize the impact of PANDORA's innovations and to encourage adoption and integration into future projects and initiatives.
7	PCL	Industrial Provider	PCL aims to target partners in the field of industrialisation companies and solution providers, which are focussing on using innovative technologies in the domains of automation and vision systems. We will showcase pandora in local events to other partners within the Netherlands. First event to showcase pandora will be the PPP gallery in Drachten on 4 dec. 2024

8	STUBA	Academic & Research	STUBA plans to disseminate the results of the PANDORA project through established channels in the domains of nuclear energy and radiation protection, ensuring sufficient scientific impact. Publications will be in the form of peer-reviewed scientific journals and presentations at scientific conferences. These published papers and conference presentations will focus on the development of trustworthy, robust, and comprehensive training datasets generated from the irradiation of passive solid-state track detectors by different particles and energies. The publications will be created within the timeframe of 2025 – 2027. Additionally, the STUBA team will disseminate the results of the PANDORA project through its activities in other European projects and organizations, such as ENEN (European Nuclear Education Network), SNETP (Sustainable Nuclear Energy Technology Platform) and ENEEP (European Nuclear Experimental Educational Platform).
9	CYU	Academic & Research	CYU plans to disseminate research results via publications in international conferences and/or journals, and presentations of research outcomes in the corresponding venues, and invited talks. The research results of CYU will be integrated in research-focused teaching and project activities as state-of-the-art approaches. CYU plans to organize targeted Workshops on Explainable AI over continuous data, in conjunction with top-notch conferences in the data management or machine learning domains. Finally, we will advertise the dissemination actions through social media for further reachability.
10	HALCOR	Industrial Provider	Halcor's dissemination plan focuses on practical, internal knowledge-sharing within its critical plant processes and extends insights from the PANDORA project across other production sites within ElvalHalcor. Key updates will be periodically shared through newsletters distributed to Halcor and ElvalHalcor S.A., ensuring that team members and partners are informed about significant milestones and project achievements. Additionally, Halcor will leverage its digital communication channels, and social media platforms, to reach broader industry and public audiences with PANDORA-related developments. Through these activities, Halcor aims to enhance awareness and understanding of trustworthy AI applications in industry, promoting both internal knowledge and external visibility.
11	CBRL	Cybersecurity, Technology Provider	CBRL plans to share findings from the PANDORA project through selected publications, with potential submissions to journals and presentations at cybersecurity-focused conferences. Our dissemination efforts will highlight advancements in analytics and anomaly detection, especially as applied within AIoT-enabled smart ecosystems. Additional engagement may include CBRL's participation in workshops and relevant events within our network, helping to bring PANDORA's outcomes to targeted industry and academic audiences effectively.
12	TSGF	Industrial Provider	TSGF will share research accomplishments through conferences and workshops as well as disseminate achievements in our engineering community.

13	UNIBO	Academic & Research	UNIBO intends to share research findings through publications in international journals and conferences, as well as by presenting the results at relevant events.
14	DLR	Academic & Research	DLR's dissemination plan aims to share our findings on advancements in quantifying and identifying uncertainty in models and data. This plan will include publishing our results in academic/scientific journals and participate to international conferences and workshops.
15	SLC	Cybersecurity, Technology consulting	SLC plans to disseminate the outcomes of the PANDORA project through targeted activities, such as presenting insights at select industry events or sharing updates via digital platforms like social media, newsletters, and the company website. The results may also be integrated into client discussions to demonstrate practical applications and innovative approaches. By focusing on efficient channels, SLC ensures the PANDORA outcomes are effectively communicated to relevant stakeholders, enhancing the project's visibility and impact.
16	TUM	Academic & Research	TUM intends to share research findings through publications in international journals and conferences, as well as by presenting the results at relevant events and including it within the teaching activities
17	IDC	Large Industry	IDC will contribute to dissemination of the project results in a threefold manner: a) we will use our positioning in associations and initiatives like BDVA to bring speaking and visibility opportunities to PANDORA, as it connects with our activities in T7.3 and T7.4; b) we will use IDC brands to create a positioning for PANDORA or technologies therein; c) we will carry out activities in support of bringing PANDORA to potential customers in specific segments (interviews, events) towards a more exploitation-focused marketing.
18	ITML	Cybersecurity, Technology Provider	ITML will disseminate its work to social media channels in a monthly basis and will provide overall support to the D&C manager. Moreover, we plan to participate in international events and fairs relevant to CS and data science, and present our research findings
19	UNSPMF	Academic & Research	UNSPMF plans to present research findings through publications in international journals and conferences, as well as by presenting the results at relevant events. Moreover, we will inform CS and Computer engineering students (at all levels) about PANDORA findings through various educational activities.
20	FRA	Industrial Provider	Framatome is committed to be active in terms of research and paper publications by sharing our research findings with PANDORA as a main focus and in acknowledgement, as well as promoting the PANDORA project within our industrial network either in exhibitions, workshops or conferences. We also commit to highlighting the benefits and outcome that the PANDORA project provides to our different clients.
21	DIE	Business, Technology & Dissemination	DIE aims to target the broad research community in the field of cybersecurity, innovative technologies in the domains of system and hardware security, IoT and cloud application development and virtualized networking domains. Furthermore, through educational activities it will target CS and Computer

			engineering students (at all levels), as well as working professionals in startups, SME and larger established companies operating at the national and European economic area.
22	EUNL	Ethics & Legal Expert	Activities oriented towards raising awareness on the constantly evolving regulatory framework and the related compliance challenges, as addressed within PANDORA, will play an important role in EUNL's dissemination strategy. Dissemination activities shall be pursued through EUNL's communication channels and active participation in scientific conferences and workshops. EUNL also aspires to produce comprehensive informative material (e.g. flyers, recommendations), as well as to coordinate the conduction of compliance educational workshops.
23	STS	Technology Provider	STS aims to disseminate the project in the communities of cybersecurity, AI & data engineering, IT/Network/Infrastructure, health IT, and software development domains, particularly through presenting the project's architecture, research objectives, and research outcomes on publicly addressed industry conferences and events. Moreover, STS has active social media channels and websites that host dissemination materials originating from PANDORA as a whole.
24	IISC	Academic & Research	IISc aims to disseminate research findings through publications in international journals and conferences and by presenting results at key events in the fields of unsupervised learning, self-supervised learning, data summarisation, and explainable machine learning
25	UOFT	Academic & Research	UofT plans to disseminate research outcomes from the PANDORA project through publications in premier journals and conferences. PANDORA's contributions will be integrated into research-led teaching and seminars, providing state-of-the-art case studies for students in fields like AI and IoT. UofT will also actively participate in international collaborative efforts to extend PANDORA's reach, aiming to establish connections with industry and academia through special sessions, panels, and workshops across Canadian and European venues, ensuring wide exposure of the project's innovative approaches.

4.2.3 Dissemination & Communication Tools

This chapter presents the tools that will be used by the project for supporting the dissemination and communication activities. The tools include the unique project identity, its web presence, its presence in the social media.

Project Identity

Figure 13: Project Identity

A clear font has been selected for the PANDORA logo. The prevailing colors are blue and yellow. With a blue text color, the design has strategic yellow highlight on the "A" and part of the "N" to emphasize "AI" within the name and is symbolic about the core values and objectives of the project.

Blue: Trust & Stability

Symbolism: The blue color is symbolic of trust, reliability, and security-values at the very core of the PANDORA project. The hue reflects the commitment of the project to the development of stable, safe, and reliable AI systems that improve data management and decision-making.

Yellow: Innovation, Optimism, and Transparency

Symbolism: Yellow is a color often associated with innovation and optimism; it further highlights the "A" and part of the "N" in PANDORA to bring into view an "AI" within the name. Blue and Yellow United: Reliable Innovation for Europe's Future.

The blue and the yellow together add to the PANDORA logo, emphasizing its twin focus on trustworthiness (blue) and innovative thinking (yellow). By highlighting "AI" in yellow, the logo visually communicates that artificial intelligence is at the heart of the project's efforts, while the blue foundation symbolizes stability and unity. Together, these are the colors and design elements that form part of a visual identity representative of PANDORA's commitment to further trustworthy AI, strengthen global competitiveness, and create a sustainable future thanks to European collaboration and technological leadership.

Project Templates

Three main templates were designed to address the needs of the project by maintaining the professionalism of the structure, the coherence in the design, and consistency throughout the project: the Deliverable template, the Presentation template, and the Use Case template.

- **Deliverable template:** This template is used for all deliverables. The initial pages contain document's metadata, including the title, status, document change history due & submission date, related WP, lead participant, contributors, reviewers, dissemination level, lead authors, and the person & boards that is authorized. Additionally, it contains a quality control table indicating the approval from the Deliverable Leader, the Project Coordinator (PC) and the QGRB Board. Following this, the Table of Contents, the Table of figures, table of Tables, a list of the Abbreviations and an executive summary are presented. The deliverable should clearly state its purpose, intended readership, and its relationship with other PANDORA work packages and management structures. At the end of the document, references and annexes are included.
- **Presentation template:** It is designed for the elaboration of project presentations. The template includes an introductory and a closing slide and contains multiple layouts to provide harmony among the presentations. Moreover, within the template, the project logo and the project's colors are used consistently.
- **Use case template:** The Use Case Template serves as a structured approach to capture essential information for each pilot scenario, even at early stages. It supports all the involved stakeholders in establishing a solid foundation for the pilot, ensuring that key details are included to guide the pilot toward successful and productive results.

Figure 14: Deliverable Template

The figure displays three pages of a document template:

- Page 1 (Cover):** Features the PANDORA logo, the text "Efficient trustworthy AI - making the best of data (AI, Data and Robotics Partnership)", "HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-CNECT", and "A Comprehensive Framework enabling the Delivery of Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation". It includes a "Document Identification" table with fields for Status, Draft, Date, Version, and Submission Date, and a table for "Document Reference" with fields for Lead Partner, Contributors, Reviewers, and Document Reference.
- Page 2 (Document Information):** Titled "The PANDORA Consortium", it contains a table listing consortium members with columns for ID, Name, Country, and Address. The table lists 25 members from various countries including Greece, Denmark, Germany, Netherlands, Slovakia, France, Cyprus, Italy, and Serbia.
- Page 3 (Table of Contents):** Lists the document's structure, including Executive Summary, Introduction, Purpose of the document, Invented relationship, Relationship with other PANDORA WPs and managing organization, Name of the Chapter, Subsection, and Name of the Chapter, with corresponding page numbers.

Figure 14: Deliverable Template

Figure 15: Presentation Template

The figure displays a presentation slide template with the following elements:

- PANDORA Logo:** Located at the top left.
- Event:** A blue box containing the word "Event".
- <Presentation Title>:** A large white box in the center for the title.
- <Partner_name>:** A white box at the bottom for the partner name.
- EU Logo and Funding Info:** Located at the bottom right, including the text "The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (Horizon) under grant agreement No 1010135775".

Figure 15: Presentation Template

Figure 16: Use Case Template

Online Material

Website and Social Media

PANDORA's website is designed with a philosophy of simplicity, focusing on delivering the fundamental information about the project. PANDORA's website is designed with a philosophy of simplicity, focusing on delivering the fundamental information about the project. The key elements include the project's objectives, the participating partners, the expected outcomes, a description of the pilots and updates on news & events. Our approach is oriented to clarity and conciseness, so as not to burden users with excessive details, yet present everything that is necessary to them.

The homepage presents core information of the project. A brief introduction to the pilot trials, expected outcomes, and the consortium. By navigating the menu, users can access more detailed information on the previously mentioned topics, as well as project-related news & events attended by the consortium. Finally, users can get in contact with PANDORA through the links directing them to the project's social media or through the contact form. A sample of the homepage is shown in the figure below.

WordPress was selected as the Content Management System based on its security, stability and the extensive variety of plugins to assist us with our objectives.

Piwik PRO has been chosen for the analytics part of the PANDORA project website. It provides a large set of functionalities, ease of use, and meets the requirements of GDPR. It provides advanced analytics with data sovereignty, storing data on servers in the EU. Piwik PRO features a user-friendly interface where every group member can access and interpret web metrics with ease. Furthermore, it contains detailed consent management mechanisms to properly attain and process the data of website visitors with complete respect for European privacy laws.

Figure 17: Detail of the PANDORA website

Figure 18: Audience Overview Statistics

Videos

YouTube was the platform chosen to host and share videos related to the project. The URL of PANDORA’s channel is: [PANDORA YouTube Channel](#). In the initial stages of the project, we aimed to provide viewers with a comprehensive understanding of the project, the problem that we aim to solve and the objectives to be attained. For that reason, the Project Coordinator, Deputy Project Coordinator, and Scientific Project Manager were chosen to present information on both the managerial aspects and the scientific approach to the problem being tackled, as well as the methods that will be used.

It was also decided that for each pilot, dedicated videos will be produced by interviewing the respective partners to provide a deeper insight into each specific pilot. During the lifecycle of the project, additional videos will be uploaded to communicate progress and achievements to a broader audience.

Figure 19: YouTube channel

Printed Material

Flyers

Aiming to generate awareness and interest in the PANDORA project at events related to AI and AIoT, including those organized by PANDORA, a four-page flyer has been developed. Designed in A5 size, the brochure will be folded for a convenient and versatile format. It contains a brief and concise summary of the PANDORA project. The PANDORA logo is featured along with a brief project description. Inside, the flyer highlights the pilot trials and expected outcomes, while the back cover lists the consortium partners including links to the project's social media channels.

PANDORA

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The PANDORA project focuses on advancing AI and data engineering to drive industrial innovation and enhance the EU economy. It addresses challenges in IoT-generated data processing, aiming to create a single data market for Europe's global competitiveness. PANDORA aims to develop AI-driven frameworks for preparing and delivering trustworthy datasets, enhancing AI models' accuracy and sustainability in AIoT systems. Its mission includes increasing autonomy, trustworthiness, and energy efficiency in managing IoT datasets for smarter and more responsive devices in smart space ecosystems.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

- PANDORA FRAMEWORK**
PANDORA Framework boosts AIoT efficiency using customizable datasets and energy-efficient services.
- INTELLIGENCE DATA PIPELINES**
Intelligence Data Pipelines streamline AI solutions by optimizing data use and enhancing efficiency.
- SYNTHETIC DATASETS**
PANDORA creates synthetic datasets using ML and NeRFs for realistic space and occupancy modeling.
- ENHANCED AI DATA**
PANDORA enhances AI data labeling and completion with minimal human effort and advanced methods.

PILOTS

- SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT (SAG)**
Distributed AI for predictive edge "apps" re-allocation in production cells.
- ERICSSON AB (EAB)**
5G-enabled smart building for semantically enhanced AI training (EAB ERICSSON).
- PHILIPS CONSUMER LIFESTYLE BV (PCL)**
AI-driven autonomous vision systems for inspecting manufactured goods.
- FRAMATOME GMBH (FRA)**
AI driven increase of safety in critical hydrogen infrastructure.
- ELVALHALCOR (HALCOR)**
Enhanced AIoT sensing infrastructures to promote energy efficiency in critical manufacturing processes.

CONSORTIUM

Logos of consortium members: IDC, TUM, HALCOR, THALES, itml, Economie Ltd., Cyberanalytics, ERICSSON, AARHUS UNIVERSITY, Sphyrne Technology Solutions, DLR, AEGIS IT RESEARCH, UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, SIEMENS, STU, framatome, ETIS, PHILIPS.

Social media links: pandora-heu.eu, @PANDORA-heu, @PandoraHeu, @PandoraHeu, Find out more

The project has received funding from the European Union's programme under Grant Agreement No. 101135775.

Figure 20: PANDORA flyer

Posters

Posters, following the same approach as the flyers, have been designed to be concise, presenting all essential information while maintaining a clean, modern aesthetic. A sample template is shown in the accompanying figure. The poster highlights the key components of the project while

emphasizing the project's mission to deliver trustworthy, AI-driven datasets that improve autonomy, trustworthiness, and sustainability for IoT ecosystems. It provides a brief description of the five user cases, the objectives and the consortium. The purpose is to present all the essential information on a single page, aimed at capturing the viewer's interest & engagement.

Figure 21: PANDORA poster

Newsletters and Press Releases

Newsletters are an important means of communication used to provide current information on the project's progress. In PANDORA, we have designed a template that aligns with the website's aesthetics, so that we have a unified presentation. The newsletters will cover topics such as participation in events, project achievements, ongoing developments and, in general, the project's progress throughout its lifecycle. A sample of the first newsletter is shown here as a matter of example.

"The Newsletter plugin" was utilized to design the email template, while the "SMTP2GO" add-on was used to manage and send the newsletters.

Figure 22: PANDORA newsletter

Press releases are a valuable tool for the dissemination strategy of PANDORA. They serve as a powerful tool to communicate the latest research milestones and the significant progress of the project. In each press release, we try to boil complex findings into simple messages that resonate with a very diverse audience—from the policymaker or industry leader all the way to academic communities and the general public. Thus, by targeting key media outlets and framing our message in terms of how this research can impact society, we can ensure with confidence that the visibility and engagement of our project's outcomes are hugely enhanced. Each press release is developed not only to inform stakeholders of the project but also to inspire broader conversations on our research topics and connect with new collaborators.

4.2.4 Dissemination and Communication Activities

This section enumerates the resources and tentative venues for the dissemination of research knowledge produced by PANDORA.

Publications

In this section a list of potential resources and venues for sharing the research outcomes developed by PANDORA will be listed. After the project's completion, certain research outputs may require extra time for final publication. This is often due to the need for validation from pilot studies or delays in the peer review process. The following sections outline various prospective venues for dissemination, including scientific conferences, workshops, journals, special issues, and other appropriate channels.

Journals

The following table presents the journals most closely aligned with PANDORA's scientific focus. While the primary emphasis is on the fields of AI and AIoT, it also covers sensors, networks, security and other relevant areas.

Table 3: List of Journals

Journal	Area	Journal Website
Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery	Data	https://link.springer.com/journal/10618
Journal of Network and Computer Applications	Network	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-network-and-computer-applications
Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical	Sensors	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/sensors-and-actuators-b-chemical
AI & Society	AI	https://link.springer.com/journal/146
ACM Transactions on Reconfigurable Technology and Systems	Systems	https://dl.acm.org/journal/trets
ACM Transactions on Privacy and Security	Security	https://dl.acm.org/journal/tops
Pervasive and Mobile Computing	Mobile	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/pervasive-and-mobile-computing
Journal Knowledge and Information Systems	Systems	https://link.springer.com/journal/10115
Computer science and information systems	Systems	http://www.comsis.org/
IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence	AI	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=34
IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems	AI	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/aboutJournal.jsp?punumber=5962385
IEEE Transactions on Artificial Intelligence	AI	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=9078688
IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology	Systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=76
IEEE Transactions on Image Processing	Image	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=83
IEEE Internet of Things journal	IoT	https://ieee-iotj.org/

Pattern Recognition	AI	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/pattern-recognition
Neural Networks	AI	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/neural-networks
Neurocomputing	AI	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/neurocomputing
Expert Systems with Applications	Systems	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/expert-systems-with-applications
Knowledge-Based Systems	Systems	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/knowledge-based-systems
Neural Computing and Applications	AI	https://link.springer.com/journal/521?gad_source=1
Pattern Recognition Letters	AI	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/pattern-recognition-letters
Neural Processing Letters	AI	https://link.springer.com/journal/11063
ACM Transactions on Internet of Things	IoT	https://dl.acm.org/journal/TIOT
ACM Transactions on Autonomous and Adaptive Systems	Systems	https://dl.acm.org/journal/taas
The International Journal on Very Large Data Bases	Data Management	https://link.springer.com/journal/778
IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering	knowledge and data engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=69
IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science	Data	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=23
Radiation Protection Dosimetry	Data	https://academic.oup.com/rpd

Special Issues

The following table outlines the suggested special issues in journals where the partners plan to publish their results.

Table 4: Special Issues

Special Issue	Journal	Submission date
Advances in Machine Learning and Data Mining: Emerging Trends and Applications	Applied Sciences, MDPI	25 February 2025

List of potential conferences

The table below presents a list of the potential conferences that the partners intend to participate in to present the results of the PANDORA project.

Table 5: List of potential conferences for PANDORA

Conferences	Site
2025 ACM SIGMETRICS conference	https://www.sigmetrics.org/sigmetrics2025/

IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)	https://2025.ieeeicip.org/
IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)	https://2025.ieeeicassp.org/
IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)	https://icc2025.ieee-icc.org/
IEEE Global Communications Conference (GlobeCom)	https://globecom2024.ieee-globecom.org/
International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR)	https://www.icprs.org/
International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)	https://2025.ijcnn.org/
European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV)	https://iser.org.in/conf/index.php?id=2642209
International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)	https://iser.org.in/conf/index.php?id=2642241
Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)	https://cvpr.thecvf.com/
IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)	https://ieee-ssci.org/
International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom)	https://www.percom.org/
ACM/IFIP International Middleware Conference	https://middleware-conf.github.io/2024/
ACM Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems	https://sensys.acm.org/2025/
ACM/IEEE Symposium on Edge Computing	https://acm-ieee-sec.org/2024/
IEEE Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IEEE CAI, 2025)	https://cai.ieee.org/2025/
IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)	https://dsaa.co/
Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)	https://neurips.cc/
Extending Database Technology (EDBT)	https://edbticdt2025.upc.edu/
Very Large Data Bases (VLDB) Conference	https://vldb.org/2025/
ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM)	http://www.cikmconference.org/
Nuclear Energy for New Europe (NENE 2025)	https://www.djs.si/nene2025
International Conference on Radiation Applications (RAP 2025)	https://www.rap-conference.org/
Computers, Privacy & Data Protection (CPDP)	https://www.cpdpconferences.org/

List of potential workshops

Table 6: List of potential workshops

Workshops	Location	Dates	Website
2025 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (IEEE CSR 2025)	Chania, Crete, Greece	August 4–6, 2025	https://www.ieee-csr.org/

2024 IEEE Workshop on Cyber Threat Intelligence and Hunting as part of the IEEE Big Data conference	Washington DC, USA (Hybrid Event)	15/12/2024 – 18/12/2024	https://www.cyberhunt2024.cyberhunt.no/
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Events

This section provides candidate EU events to be joined by PANDORA partners as well as workshops or other events organized by the partners. Using these events PANDORA will try to maximize its visibility in research, academia and industrial communities by showcasing and demonstrating its objectives, novel concepts and results. Notice that some of them necessarily overlap with activities reported under collaboration or clustering or even international cooperation when such elements are involved in generating the dissemination opportunity.

Participation in EU Events

Table 7: List of EU events

EU Event	Location	Dates	Website
European Big Data Value Forum	Budapest, Hungary	2-4 October 2024	https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/
AI, Data, Robotics Forum, European Sovereignty in AI, Data and Robotics	Eindhoven, Netherlands	04-05 November 2024 (Participated)	https://adrforum.eu/
FORUM INCYBER EUROPE	Lille, France	1-3 April 2025	https://europe.forum-incyber.com/
Barcelona Cybersecurity Congress	Barcelona, Spain	13-15 May 2025	https://www.barcelonacybersecuritycongress.com/
Annual Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Fundamental Rights 2025	Online	7-9 April 2025	https://www.era.int/cgi-bin/cms?_SID=5533e23a3a1c1043628ea47ec37d50b99980719301126822460329&sprache=en&bereich=artikel&aktion=detail&idartikel=133262

Hosting Workshops and Other Events

The following table lists all the workshops that PANDORA is planning to organize.

Table 8: List of workshops

Workshop/Events organized by PANDORA partners	Location	Dates	Website
Distributed and Continual Inference and Learning (Special Session at MLSP 2024)	London, UK	22-25 September (Participated)	https://2024.ieeemlsp.org/ https://sites.google.com/view/dc-il-2024

<p>Enabling Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation Mathematical methods for explainable AI Talk Title: Enabling Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation</p>	<p>Munich Germany</p>	<p>14 October 2024</p>	<p>https://sites.google.com/view/ecmi-xai/home</p>
<p>Forging Trust in Artificial Intelligence, IJCNN Workshops (to be submitted)</p>	<p>Rome</p>	<p>30 June 2025 – 5 July 2025</p>	

Other Events

Other events that are outside of the scope of the previously mentioned will be organized. These events will demonstrate PANDORA’s results and the progress of the pilots. They will be planned at a latter phase of the project when the pilots are in a demonstratable phase.

4.3 Collaboration: clustering and Networking

4.3.1 Objectives

Clustering and Networking are two of the vehicles and mechanisms that PANDORA will use to maximize the impact of the project; as such, they serve means rather than results, and consequently, they link directly to other activities within this WP, especially dissemination and communication, but also exploitation. In essence, they can be considered levers for the success of the project from the impact viewpoint.

Generally speaking, the main objectives are:

- Making the project visible to other communities and getting aware of initiatives and projects that are of relevance to PANDORA.
- Capitalizing networks and projects to improve our Dissemination & Communication KPIs. This includes the generation of more content and activity in social media, opening opportunities for joint publications, workshops and presence at events.
- Ensuring alignment with the research landscape and defining the positioning of PANDORA within the myriads of research and innovation projects and initiatives so that we are better at defining messages that highlight the specificities and added value of PANDORA with respect to others.
- Identifying opportunities for joint implementation or improved execution of our activities. This could range from reusing a technology or component produced by another project and discovered as a result of these activities (leading to a more efficient use of resources), to the usage of any of the assets of PANDORA by others, or replication of Use Cases.
- Opening opportunities for exploitation of the project results. This can happen because of better understanding of the target market or identification of specific exploitation opportunities.

As can be seen, all these objectives are tightly connected with other activities in WP7, but also with other WPs. So, the impact of networking and clustering for PANDORA will be measurable in the areas above, and thus, should result in more efficient implementation, D&C indicators or exploitation prospects.

Beyond impact, these activities can also be measured in terms of performance, and here (even though overlapping with some other KPI of the project), we have dared to define several performance indicators that will be revised along the project duration based on evolving needs, requirements and context.

Performance indicators for networking and clustering:

- Number of projects PANDORA has engaged with: 6
- Number of initiatives (clusters, associations and other entities not falling under the category of projects) reached out during the project: 4
- Workshops/events resulted from networking and clustering activities: 6
- Other achievements, like assets generated because of collaboration with others (e.g. joint papers): 2

4.3.2 Methodological Approach

- **Landscaping:** understanding existing networks and the research context of interest to PANDORA.
- **Identification of priorities:** selection of those projects and initiatives with the highest potential so that we can maximize the return on investment (as mentioned above, while the performance of networking and clustering activities can be measured by giving indicators of activities carried out, the most important motivation is the effect that those activities could create in our project).
- **Opportunity scouting:** work with the initiatives and projects prioritized in the previous point (others may also be considered as they fit, if still part of the landscape) to create opportunities for joint visibility, exchange of knowledge or potential work on a common asset.
- **Planning:** once an opportunity is identified (e.g., Organization of a workshop between different projects at a relevant event), we plan the team and work to be done (this normally entails appointing an individual or a team to feed content and do some organizational work).
- **Implementation and materialization of opportunities:** implementation of the activities
- **Monitoring and revision of the strategy and planning:** this step will be taken periodically in the project, normally on a yearly basis, so that we can assess the outcomes of our work and identify areas where improvements are needed. This would ideally be input for the overall revision of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy. In the case of PANDORA, this will be documented in D7.2.

4.3.3 Developments in the initial phase of the project

Based on the methodological approach described above, the following content reports the activities carried out so far in the initial phase of the project (M1-M9).

4.3.3.1 *Landscaping analysis (stakeholder characterization map)*

AI, Data and Robotics Partnership and ADRA

General description

ADRA is the AI, Data and Robotics Association that acts as the private side of the European Partnership on AI, Data and Robotics. The partnership was formally established in June 2021, with the signature of a MoU between ADRA and the European Commission. ADRA is a legal entity and as such, it is governed by a Board of Directors that includes experts of the three disciplines (AI, Data, Robotics) representing both the research and the industry side so that a complete picture can be achieved about competitiveness and research challenges. You may realize that some associations and initiatives were already working on these topics prior to the foundation of ADRA. In fact, the initiative was founded by major European players in such areas

-including the Big Data Value Association BDVA, the European Robotics Association euRobotics, the European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems ELLIS, European Association for Artificial Intelligence EurAI, and the Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe CALrne, formerly known as CLAIRE-, driven by the need of joining forces due to technology convergence, and hopefully leading to more efficient and effective outcomes of the European research and innovation community in AI.

Main priorities

The reference document for the work of ADRA is the SRIDA (Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda). This document features the vision for ADR technologies in 2030, major trends and gaps, and the strategic plan for the period 2025-2027 in its latest version (4th edition of SRIDA). Based on this work elaborated by consensus, these are the main priorities:

- Ground-breaking technological foundations in ADR (autonomy, high-performance and predictability)
- Effective and Trustworthy General-Purpose ADR (generative AI, neuro-symbolic AI, generality, continual learning, trust, scale and complexity)
- An interoperable and integrated framework for data and model ecosystems (operations, governance, privacy, and security)
- Next-generation smart embodied robotic systems (soft robotics, autonomy, manipulation, configurability, human robot interaction and lifelong learning)
- Developing ADR technology for the sciences (from data to knowledge and understanding)
- Research, innovation, and tools for compliance (trust, privacy, security beyond compliance)

Working structure

The structure of the work in ADRA revolves around specific working groups. Topic groups include: i) energy, ii) agrifood, iii) Generative AI for robots, iv) Legal topic group, v) ecosystem mapping and information repository, vi) healthcare, vii) Generative AI for manufacturing, viii) Digital Twin automation and Logistics for the factory, ix) mobility and smart urban spaces, x) innovation, deployment and uptake of ADR technologies, xi) education, future of work and societal transformation, xii) inspection and maintenance, xiii) Strategic Research, Innovation and deployment agenda (focused on the evolution of the SRIDA), xiv) Policy and xv) Standardisation.

While many of them are of great interest, contributions are difficult because they require partners to be formal members of the initiative.

ADRA also injects content into other initiatives, such as GenerativeAI4EU, a European Union program aimed at promoting the development and adoption of generative artificial intelligence across key industrial sectors in Europe.

Finally, while ADRA provides the conceptual framework for the work of the founding associations and members of the legal entity, it also relies on a project that acts as operational arm -or at least to some extent- called ADRA-e, whose aim is to support the ecosystem and promote many of the content activities mentioned before by nurturing relationships between projects, organizing events and others. This is one of the tools that PANDORA has used so far, as depicted later in this document.

Reference documents

As mentioned before, the main document to consider for alignment is the SRIDA (at the time of releasing this document, the reference is the fourth edition). In addition, other reports can be found on the ADRA-e project website.

Tools for networking and engagement facilitation: flagship events and other communication channels

The flagship event of the initiative is the so-called European AI, Data and Robotics forum. Other workshops including brokerage sessions add to the picture.

As it has been described, ADRA builds upon capabilities of key associations or initiatives working on AI, data or robotics. While all of them could add value to PANDORA, at this stage of the project, we will describe just some of them (selected because of not only research but also industrial focus, capability for PANDORA to make use of their resources and effectively engage, etc.). A more detailed analysis will be done in the next period as needed based on the evolution of the project.

BDVA (Big Data Value Association)

General description

BDVA is a legal entity that was created in 2014 with a similar purpose than the one described for ADRA, but in this case, to become the private counterpart of the Big Data Value Public Private Partnership. In that role, BDVA has played an instrumental role in nurturing and supporting the data ecosystem in Europe. It has released periodic versions of its SRIDA, as well as many other thematic documents. As with the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership, at the beginning, it also had a CSA helping in operations (the BDVe project). This was especially important in order to manage and build upon the contents created by a huge portfolio of data-related projects which included large scale pilots or lighthouse projects, actions to build data hubs (i-spaces), research actions as well as innovation actions, among others.

As main definition, BDVA is an industry-driven research and innovation organization with a mission to develop an innovation ecosystem that enables the data-driven and AI-enabled digital transformation of the economy and society in Europe. As data is a key enabler for AI, in the last years, BDVA has placed itself as a cornerstone of the development of AI technologies as well as platforms to foster data sharing (such as data spaces) or measures to be regulatory compliance, since the last years have been especially active in the development of data policies and regulations.

Main priorities

The last updates of the BDVA agenda (from 2024) reflect the following topics as the top priorities:

- Empowering European industries and societies for a human-centric digital future
- Expanding data-driven ecosystems across sectors and (global) value chains
- Making data and AI innovations fit for emerging infrastructures and platforms
- Sustainable data and AI: enhancing efficiency and resilience while reducing resource demands
- Integrating innovation, ethics and compliance

Working structure

The structure of work of BDVA is based on Task Forces that address challenges in specific topics or domains.

- Foundational task forces include the development of the community and ecosystem as well as the updates of the program, looking at roadmap and SRIDA.
- Cross-sectorial task forces tackle fields like Business, Data and AI Technologies, Data Protection, Data Spaces, Emerging Topics, Etami (this will appear later on in this document), Generative AI and Foundation models, HPC, Big Data and AI, i-Spaces, Policy and Societal, Skills, Standards and Benchmarking.
- Sector-specific task forces, as the number indicates, look at the specific challenges of creating value out of data in different applications and domains. The following ones are

currently part of the portfolio: Agrifood, Automotive, Earth Observation and Geospatial, Energy, Finance, Healthcare, Media, Mobility and Logistics, Security, Smart Governance and Smart Cities, Smart Manufacturing Industry, Telecom.

This structure of task forces complements ad-hoc groups created for specific purposes but also the ongoing activity of governance bodies like the BoD and in particular the Technical Board.

In the case of BDVA, of particular interest are the collaborations established through formal partnerships with other flagship initiatives, notably -and beyond the AI, Data and Robotics partnership aforementioned-, the EuroHPC JU or the Data Space Business Alliance (DSBA), composed of several organizations that are leading developments on data spaces such as GAIA-X, IDSA and FIWARE.

Reference documents

The SRIDA in its different versions guides the strategy of BDVA, complemented by actions in areas like the federation of i-Spaces (as a testing facility for data-driven innovations) and the numerous papers and reports published by task forces.

Tools for networking and engagement facilitation: flagship events and other communication channels

BDVA is very active in promoting networking and helping in project clustering. We can see later that PANDORA has used these resources to promote relationships with other projects and initiatives and create awareness about its work.

This mainly happens through several flagship events run by the association, namely the Data Week and European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF). It also supports and co-organizes other events in relation to partnerships. From these ones, beyond the support to the events led by ADRA, it may be worth highlighting the Data Spaces Symposium (co-organized with the institutions of the Data Spaces Business Alliance and the flagship project of the EC that governs and provides guidance for the deployment of data spaces, the Data Spaces Support Center).

The Data week has evolved in the last years and sometimes it is distributed along different periods of the year (so, several events are coined under that branding, with one of them always happening in spring), while EBDVF is always placed around October-November and the location follows the country that holds the EU Presidency, thus, getting explicit support from Member States.

AI Communities

CAIRNE, eurAI and ELLIS are the three research-oriented associations focused on AI that contributed to the setup of the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership and hence, ADRA. While they will be further analysed in the next period of the project to better understand the opportunities of PANDORA in their networks (if any), we provide here a short overview of the three of them:

- **CAIRNE (former CLAIRE):** the focus of CAIRNE is on strengthening European excellence in AI by creating a vibrant and collaborative AI ecosystem that prioritizes human-centered, trustworthy, and responsible AI. Human-centricity translates into a big attention to ethical principles, sustainability, and societal well-being. Collaboration is promoted between research institutions, industry, and policymakers looking to ensure European sovereignty. CAIRNE also tackles the challenge of getting robust AI infrastructures in Europe as well as the creation of a Large-Scale AI Research Hub (or *CERN for AI*, as they call it).
- **eurAI:** the European Association for European Artificial Intelligence is an international association with scientific and educational objectives called European Coordinating Committee for Artificial Intelligence (ECCAI). As a non-for-profit organization, its main objectives are: to promote the science and technology of artificial intelligence in Europe;

To promote the establishment of a European computer network; To encourage the teaching of artificial intelligence; To publish a European journal of information on artificial intelligence and to sponsor a biennial conference organized by one or more of the members, generally scientific European associations concerned with artificial intelligence. They must have at least 25 members actively working in this field to become members.

- **ELLIS**: the European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems - is a pan-European AI network of excellence which focuses on fundamental science, technical innovation and societal impact. Founded in 2018, ELLIS builds upon machine learning as the driver for modern AI and aims to secure Europe's sovereignty in this competitive field by creating a multi-centric AI research laboratory. ELLIS wants to ensure that the highest level of AI research is performed in the open societies of Europe and follows a three-pillar strategy to achieve that: the ELLIS Research Programs, ELLIS PhD and post-doc program and the ELLIS sites.

From this description we may think about overlaps among these associations, which is probably the case. Being AI such an important topic, this is probably a minor problem provided they are well coordinated in their activities so that resources are used in the most efficient way for maximum impact.

euRobotics

General description

euRobotics is a non-profit association for stakeholders in European robotics. As in the case of BDVA, its origin is old and was part of the Public-Private Partnership SPARC under Horizon2020. Main goals can be summarized as: strengthening competitiveness and ensuring industrial leadership of manufacturers, providers and end users of robotics technology-based systems and services; best uptake of robotics technologies and services for professional and private use; and fostering excellence of the science base of European robotics.

Main priorities

The document 'A Unified Vision for European Robotics' points out the main challenges and recommendations from the robotics community. The goals are: capitalise on Europe's leading position; fully leverage the robotics expertise; ensure progress in AI is focused on the needs of robotics; better connect, not merge, the different robotics related ecosystems; adopt a far more active approach to technology investments; deploy more robots more widely, maintain a technology edge in robotics; and educate and train the current and future workforce. To address them, euRobotics has defined a series of recommendations that will help to implement its strategy, namely i) make Robotics a policy priority; ii) increase the scale and agility of investment in research and innovation; iii) focus long-term support on the unique challenges of robotics uptake; iv) stimulate collaboration between end users, technology innovators, and research; v) recognise and actively support the full robotics innovation pathway; vi) maintain sovereignty over robotics capabilities through alignment between Member State and EC initiatives and the private sector; vii) create a European skills framework, viii) provide tailored support for robotics scale-up; and iv) improve societal awareness and acceptance of the need for robotics.

Working structure

As in the previous case, the work is realized through a series of working groups, known here as topic groups. The active list is amazing, including: Agriculture, Healthcare, Industrial Robotics, Logistics and Transport, Robot Companions for Assisted Living, Space Robotics, Construction, Laboratory Robotics, Inspection and Maintenance, Marine Robotics, Aerial Robotics, Bio-Inspired Robotics, Miniaturised Robots, Standardisation, Wearable Robotics, Harsh Environment Robotics, Safety, AI and Cognition, Autonomous Navigation, Mechatronics, Software

Engineering, Systems Integration and Systems Engineering, Perception, Socially Intelligent Robotics and Societal Applications, Sustainability, Telerobotics and Teleoperation, Cloud Robotics, Cybersecurity, Education and Training, Entrepreneurship, Ethical Legal and Socio-Economic, Benchmarking and Competitions.

Reference documents

The current strategy is documented in the document “A Unified Vision for European Robotics”.

Tools for networking and engagement facilitation: flagship events and other communication channels

euRobotics as a long track record of events for the community, being the most important ones the European Robotics Forum (main meeting of the robotics community in the EU), the European Robotics Week (with activities for the general public), European Robotics League and the euRobotics awards.

euCloudEdgelot.eu (European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum Initiative)

Just a short overview of a research area that is very important to the AI developments in general and PANDORA in particular and could be less known to this community because of the fragmentation of the research landscape. The EUCloudEdgelot.eu initiative aims to realise a pathway for the understanding and development of the Cloud, Edge and IoT (CEI) Continuum by promoting cooperation between a wide range of research projects, developers and suppliers, business users and potential adopters of this new technological paradigm. Very few cases nowadays work exclusively on the cloud or the edge, and we can easily find hybrid ecosystems where companies have to deal with the so-called computing continuum. This brings additional requirements to the technologies and their deployments in pilots. We wanted to highlight this initiative because it plays a community building role, as it was the case for most associations so far (even though in this case there is not a legal entity but a group of projects whose coordination is mandated to some CSA projects). The initiative puts a great focus on standardisation as well as on both the supply and demand sides of the computing continuum. A high number of projects are included in the portfolio, some of them include rich content that PANDORA could capitalize.

While many other technology associations exist, we think the ones described so far constitute the main focus for PANDORA. However, it is interesting to look at the perspective of the domains included in our pilots, or at least some of them. At EU level and in some cases at the national level, we can find associations that work on the priorities affecting stakeholders in specific industries. Especially relevant are the initiatives around manufacturing. Data and AI are becoming increasingly relevant in their developments and investments, and thus, we have made a brief analysis of some references to be used by our project for validation, awareness, synergy creation or global outreach.

EFFRA (European Factories of the Future Research Association)

General description

EFFRA is a non-for-profit, industry-driven association promoting the development of new and innovative production technologies. EFFRA has been representing the private side of the manufacturing partnership with the EU Commission. Named under Horizon 2020, Factories of the Future to become Made in Europe nowadays under Horizon Europe. Manufacturing is of key importance for Europe, employing 29.4 million persons in 2020 and being the largest contributor to non-financial business economy value added, accounting for more than one quarter of the total (29 %). Because manufacturing can help in keeping added-value jobs in Europe, ensuring our

resilience and promoting sustainability, EFFRA provides a cross-sectorial platform that enables collaboration between stakeholders at European level. More than 150 members and a portfolio of more than 88 projects are key assets of EFFRA.

Main priorities

Main objectives and topics included within the agenda of this partnership include:

- Excellent, responsive and smart factories and supply chain. Topics: Zero-defect and zero-down-time high precision manufacturing, including predictive quality and non-destructive inspection methods; Manufacturing for miniaturisation and functional Integration; Scalable, reconfigurable and flexible first-time right manufacturing, Artificial intelligence for productive, excellent, robust and agile manufacturing chains; Advanced manufacturing processes for smart and complex products; Data ‘highways’ and data spaces in support of smart factories in dynamic value networks.
- Circular products & Climate-neutral manufacturing. Topics: Ultra-efficient, low energy and carbon manufacturing; De-manufacturing, re-manufacturing and recycling technologies for circular economy; Manufacturing with new and substitute materials; Virtual end-to-end life-cycle engineering and manufacturing from product to production lines, factories, and networks; Digital platforms and data management for circular product and production-systems life-cycles; Predictive Manufacturing capabilities & Logistics of the future.
- New integrated business, product-service and production approaches; new use models. Topics: Collaborative product-service engineering for customer driven manufacturing value networks; Manufacturing processes and approaches near to customers or consumers (including urban manufacturing); Transparency, trust and data integrity along the product and manufacturing life-cycle; Secure communication and IP management for smart factories in dynamic value networks.
- Human-centred and human-driven manufacturing innovation. Topics: Digital platforms and engineering tools supporting creativity and productivity of research & development processes; Improving human device interaction using augmented and virtual reality and digital twins; Human & technology complementarity and excellence in manufacturing; Manufacturing Innovation and change management; Technology validation and migration paths towards full industrial deployment of advanced manufacturing technologies by SMEs.

While some topics are far from PANDORA, we can easily realize that some others fall under the fields of our project, with pilots that can be especially relevant to exemplify the use of some technologies in manufacturing.

Working structure

The work of members is structured around a number of working groups:

- Productive and Flexible Manufacturing
- Circularity and Re-Manufacturing
- Humans in the Workplace
- Energy Sector Needs
- Transport Sector Needs
- Exploitation of Research Results

Reference documents

Main documents to consider in this case are: “Made in Europe guidance document”, the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), and the “Made in Europe Partnership draft proposal”.

Tools for networking and engagement facilitation: flagship events and other communication channels

EFFRA features an Innovation Portal that includes outcomes from ongoing and past projects and is a great knowledge base for the aforementioned topics.

The association also includes Brokerage and matchmaking opportunities, Interactive webinars and expert working groups, normally open just to members.

Manufacturing-X

General description

Manufacturing-X is an initiative to digitalize supply chains in the industry. It relates to the well-known Industry 4.0 platform, whose stakeholders have the goal to implement the Data Space Industrie 4.0 and the transformation to a digitally networked industry across the board. Business, politics and academia have started the joint initiative Manufacturing-X. Companies will become able to autonomously and jointly use data across the entire production and supply chain, making digital innovations possible for more resilience, sustainability and competitiveness. The initiative counts on activities implemented at local, regional, national and international level.

Main priorities

Main goals around the deployment of a truly data space for Industry entail: the creation of new business models for a sustainable economy (e.g. closed circular economy, transparency about the carbon footprint and higher efficiency (sustainability)); reorganization of value networks to react quickly to disruptions (resilience) and security and expansion of the global leadership position of European and especially German industry with digital innovations (competitiveness).

Working structure

While this needs to be further analysed by Pandora to better understand the feasibility of engaging in some activities of Manufacturing-X, some working groups are highlighted on the website as a reference of the content areas:

- Reference Architectures and Standards
- Technology and Application Scenarios
- Security of Networked Systems
- Legal Framework
- Work, Education and Training
- Digital Business Models in Industry 4.0

Reference documents

2030 Vision for Industrie 4.0

Tools for networking and engagement facilitation: flagship events and other communication channels

The initiative has a governance structure with different layers of responsibilities and activities, going from a research council to the working groups and including test labs and international cooperation. PANDORA is having discussions now to understand the convenience, effort and feasibility of potential engagement.

PROJECTS (including short overview)

Finally, while associations, partnerships and other initiatives are instrumental for networking and for driving a joint vision, it is of the interest of PANDORA to understand what the peer projects in particular are doing, which complementarities there could be and what is the positioning that PANDORA could develop in this research context. Some other projects add to the criterium of

relevance to PANDORA. The identification of main projects and a short description of their coverage are presented below:

Sister projects (projects funded under the same topic as PANDORA)

PANDORA belongs to the set of projects selected under the topic HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-01. Efficient trustworthy AI - making the best of data, contributing to realize the objectives of the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership.

All of them are expected to contribute to the following outcomes, as described by the topic in the corresponding work program:

- Optimised AI solutions: optimising model design and data usage to maximize accuracy and robustness.
- Ensure in general, the pipeline of high-quality, representative, unbiased and compliant training data for AI development in all relevant sectors
- Support data preparation and AI training processes that lead to efficient and more trustworthy AI

The other projects awarded under this topic are: **MANOLO, EXTRA-BRAIN, RAIDO and AI-ADAPT.**

MANOLO (Trustworthy Efficient AI for Cloud-Edge Computing)

The overall objective of MANOLO is to deliver a complete and trustworthy stack of algorithms and tools to help AI systems reach better efficiency and seamless optimisation in their operations, resources and data required to train, deploy and run high-quality and lighter AI models in both centralised and cloud-edge distributed environments. MANOLO will push the state of the art in the development of a collection of complementary algorithms for training, understanding, compressing and optimising machine learning models by advancing research in the areas of model compression, meta-learning and domain adaptation, frugal neural network search and growth and neuromorphic models.

MANOLO will develop a data management framework for distributed tracking of assets and their provenance (data, models, algorithms) together with a benchmark framework to monitor, evaluate and compare new AI algorithms and deployments, along with explainability, robustness and security mechanisms to evaluate and augment the trustworthiness of the models and system.

EXTRA-BRAIN (Explainable Trustworthy Brain-like AI for Data Intensive Applications)

EXTRA-BRAIN aims to develop, validate, and deploy optimised AI solutions based on scalable brain-like neural networks. Unlike conventional deep learning, which is resource-intensive and dependent on large, annotated datasets, EXTRA-BRAIN focuses on AI methods that offer low-power consumption, dynamic scalability, deployment flexibility, efficient learning, and continuous adaptation. The project leverages insights from neuroscience to create AI solutions that mimic brain functionality, particularly in perception and cognition. Its key objectives include advancing energy-efficient neuromorphic computing for the edge-cloud continuum and demonstrating real-world applications in robotics, telecommunications, and financial analytics. The project emphasizes a human-centric AI design that prioritizes transparency, trustworthiness, and explainability.

RAIDO (Reliable AI and Data Optimisation)

RAIDO aims to provide a comprehensive framework for Trustworthy and Green-AI by offering a holistic solution that covers all data and model-related aspects, within an integrated platform. It offers automated data curation and enrichment methods, such as Digital Twins and diffusion models, to ensure high-quality, representative, unbiased, and compliant training data for trustworthy AI model development. The platform also offers data-/compute-efficient models and tools for energy-efficient Green AI. Transparency, explainability (XAI), and soundness of optimised AI models, along with proper data handling processes are ensured through various XAI methods, decentralized blockchain and feedback-based reinforcement learning.

The RAIDO platform aims to provide novel KPIs and to support adaptive human in-the-loop (HiTL) interactions through novel visualization techniques, also emphasizing the construction of dynamic interfaces to support appropriate AI paradigms. RAIDO organizes the work around the following pillars: automated enrichment of data for AI, Data and compute efficient models and AI orchestrator, ethical and unbiased data for trustworthy AI training and AI explainability, and finally, flexible and energy efficient E2C deployment powered by an AI orchestrator.

AI-ADAPT (AI-Ops Framework for Automated, Intelligent and Reliable Data/AI Pipelines Lifecycle with Humans in-the-Loop and Coupling of Hybrid Science-Guided and AI Models)

AI-DAPT aims to develop an AIOps framework to automate AI pipelines with a data-centric approach. It focuses on two key axes: data, using Explainable AI (XAI) for automation, synthetic data generation, and observability; and AI/model, integrating data-driven AI with science-based models for high-quality insights. The project's main objectives include automating data lifecycle operations, creating interoperable AI management pipelines, ensuring fair and trusted hybrid science-AI models, and developing the AI-DAPT AIOps platform to enable reliable and efficient AI/data pipelines.

While the former projects seem the focus for our networking and clustering activities, other projects seem relevant to PANDORA and will be further analysed. It may be the case that some projects have finished or will be over during the course of PANDORA project. These circumstances will also be part of our planning but including them in the landscape analysis could lead us to interesting resources and follow-up actions. For example, the EUHubs4Data project mentioned below brings a very interesting ecosystem of data-driven hubs that could help us with validation activities, and even if the project is finished, they still collaborate under the umbrella of the federation of i-Spaces within BDVA. Projects highlighted here are recognized as important ones in some of the fields of reference of the AI partnership.

EUHubs4Data (Data)

EUHubs4Data stands for European federation of Data-Driven Innovation Hubs with the aim to advance data-driven innovation and experimentation across Europe. By fostering collaboration among data initiatives, the project created a comprehensive catalogue of data services and datasets, promoting cross-border and cross-sector data sharing. This initiative aimed to support European SMEs and start-ups by providing access to federated data services and contributing to the development of common European data spaces. The federation initially comprised 12 Digital Innovation Hubs across 10 countries and 12 regions, with plans for further expansion. Throughout its duration, EUHubs4Data launched open calls to support data-driven experiments and engaged with various stakeholders to strengthen the European data ecosystem.

DSSC (Data)

The Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) aims to accelerate the formation of sovereign data spaces as a crucial element of digital transformation across various sectors. It provides support to public sector entities and companies interested in creating interoperable data frameworks that facilitate secure data transactions among participants. The DSSC offers resources such as a knowledge base, toolboxes, and a help desk to assist data space initiatives at different maturity levels. Additionally, it has developed a comprehensive blueprint to guide emerging data spaces through various development phases, ensuring compliance with common governance principles, standards, and best practices.

VISION (AI)

The VISION project aims to strengthen, connect, and mobilize Europe's AI community to position Europe as a global leader in AI research, development, and deployment. By fostering collaboration among the European networks of AI excellence centers (NoEs), VISION seeks to create a world-class AI ecosystem that emphasizes human-centric, ethical, and trustworthy AI. The project builds upon the successes of initiatives like CLAIRE and AI4EU, leveraging Europe's strong research community to maintain strategic autonomy in AI. Key activities include organizing Theme Development Workshops to identify AI challenges, developing a joint Strategic Research Agenda, and facilitating cooperation between academia and industry. Through these efforts, VISION aims to ensure Europe remains at the forefront of AI advancements.

AI4Europe (AI)

The AI4Europe project focuses on enhancing and expanding the existing AI ecosystem through the AI-on-Demand (AIoD) platform. Building upon the foundation laid by the AI4EU project, AI4Europe works on fostering collaboration among researchers, academics, SMEs, and industry stakeholders to advance AI research and innovation in Europe. Key objectives include increasing shared research efforts, developing a sustainable model for the platform's long-term viability, ensuring interoperability with existing platforms, and enriching the platform's repository with diverse AI assets. By addressing these goals, AI4Europe seeks to position Europe as a leader in human-centric and trustworthy AI, facilitating the development and deployment of AI technologies across various sectors.

AI-BOOST

AI-BOOST is an EU-funded prominent open challenge prize programme, which is a pioneering open challenge prize programme designed to set a benchmark for the European AI community. Its core objective is to organize and execute highly replicable AI open innovation competitions that attract top-tier talent across the EU and Associated Countries. By fostering collaboration among key AI stakeholders, AI-BOOST aims to define impactful AI challenges that lead to trustworthy, human-centric real-world solutions. This initiative is particularly relevant to PANDORA, as both projects emphasize scientific progress, AI-driven innovation, and community engagement. AI-BOOST's methodology, infrastructure support, and focus on high-impact AI challenges align with PANDORA's mission, offering valuable dissemination opportunities and potential synergies in advancing AI research and adoption.

The 6 Network of Excellence centers in AI: Tailor, AI4Media, HumaneAINet, Elise, euROBIN, ELSA

The EC has funded 6 Networks of Excellence Centers in AI, with each network focusing on specific aspects of AI to strengthen Europe's position in this field:

- **TAILOR:** Aims to create a scientific network on the foundations of trustworthy AI by integrating learning, optimisation, and reasoning. TAILOR seeks to reduce fragmentation and enhance Europe's joint AI research capacity, advancing the state-of-the-art in trustworthy AI.
- **AI4Media:** Focuses on AI for media, society, and democracy. The project aims to strengthen Europe's excellence in AI by developing ethical and trustworthy AI solutions tailored to the media sector, addressing challenges like disinformation and enhancing content creation and distribution.
- **HumanE-AI-Net:** Dedicated to developing human-centered AI that enhances human capabilities and empowers individuals. The network emphasizes ethical AI development, ensuring that AI systems are transparent, fair, and aligned with human values.
- **ELISE:** Concentrates on machine learning and AI, bringing together leading European researchers to tackle major scientific and technological challenges. ELISE aims to foster collaboration between academia and industry, promoting the deployment of AI-based solutions across various sectors.
- **euROBIN:** Focuses on advancing robotics and AI integration, aiming to create a unified European robotics community. The network seeks to develop innovative robotic technologies and applications, enhancing Europe's competitiveness in the global robotics market.
- **ELSA:** Centers on the development of AI solutions that are ethical, legal, and socially acceptable. The network addresses the societal impacts of AI, ensuring that AI technologies are developed and deployed in ways that respect fundamental rights and societal values.

The information provided in this section shows the complexity of the AI ecosystem in Europe, with many initiatives and projects that are difficult to follow and potential overlaps and inefficiencies in terms of operations and impact. It is not the role of PANDORA to influence this, but to use the available instruments for the benefit of the project. This chapter is an initial version of the landscape characterization for PANDORA and will be periodically revisited and enriched on the basis of the evolution of the AI picture (see the wider ecosystem in the illustrations below).

Figure 23: The European AI Landscape presented at ERF2023 (source: AI4Europe; also included in D2.1 Report on online repository of ADR related projects of the ADRA-e project)

Figure 24: Draft of an overview of AI, Data and Robotics ecosystem in Europe, organized by the relevant EU instruments. (source: D2.1 Report on online repository of ADR related projects of the ADRA-e project)

4.3.3.2 Opportunity scouting and Planning

The landscape analysis produced in the previous version is the starting point of our decision-making process with respect to where to focus the networking and clustering work in PANDORA. While the landscape will be further detailed and updated during the course of the project and more concrete organizations and stakeholders will be identified within those initiatives and possibly other new ones, we are already in a position to identify the priorities in terms of opportunities for PANDORA for the first half of the project, when technologies and pilots are still in the early development phase. This plan will be revisited periodically.

Our work will be aligned with the dissemination task but will respond to different interests based on two periods:

- **First half of the project (M1-M18):** PANDORA will be addressing main research challenges in the first part of the project, completing milestones around the scientific achievements for trustworthy training data sets and services for AIoT systems; the project will also get its first instantiation of the PANDORA framework as an integrated framework and instantiation of data pipelines in industrial settings.
 - **Set of initiatives/projects to engage with:** projects funded under the same topic, i.e., “sister projects to PANDORA” (MANOLO, EXTRA-BRAIN, RAIDO, AI-BOOST and AI-ADAPT); big initiatives shaping the fields of data and AI, notably ADRA and BDVA; exploration of projects like AI4Europe and some of the initiatives listed above with activities aiming to support the ecosystem, and thus offering opportunities for visibility and interaction.
 - **Rational:** as our speech will be oriented towards expected outcomes and initial scientific approaches, we should not *kill* audiences that may be interested in “experiencing” and “touching” results. Our main aim should be to make PANDORA known in the community, to get to know the closest projects so that we can elaborate a clear value proposition with differential elements with respect to our peers and thus, to define the positioning of PANDORA in the AI ecosystem. This should also be helpful to find additional synergies for research and development aspects. The focus will then be on identifying and materializing opportunities for visibility, awareness and knowledge exchange such as webinars, workshops, newsletters and events.
- **Second half of the project (M19-M36):** in this period, the technical basis of the project will be sound and stable, with more work focused on execution and assessment of the experiments, industrial uptake and reflections on sustainability.
 - **Set of initiatives/projects to engage with:** once the priorities for clustering and networking are well developed, they will still be capitalized and others will add to our plan, including the list above and others that may emerge; AI4Europe will be a specific target here. The umbrella of associations will expand from ADRA and BDVA as main target in the first part of the project to a wider ecosystem, including EFFRA or Manufacturing-X (they are part of our list above), but also others in the Telecom sector, critical infrastructures and additional domains where PANDORA could be relevant. Instruments like DIHs will be approached by PANDORA and other -more industrial and closer to the market- organizations such as Chambers of Commerce, will be reached out by partners.
 - **Rational:** A more intense activity will go to instruments that help us to validate the PANDORA results with external constituencies and potential uptake of results, addressing not only technologies but also the deployment of solutions to address very concrete challenges and requirements in industrial domains, as this will help us to disseminate the pilot work and position PANDORA as a solution in such environments. The focus in the second part of the project will then be on

communicating our key results and evolution of project achievements, relating to stakeholders for validation, exploitation of synergies that make us more efficient or effective and exploitation, uptake and sustainability.

4.3.3.3 *Implementation of opportunities*

This section summarizes some of the activities carried out by PANDORA according to the plan for networking and clustering described in the previous sections.

ETAMI represented in PANDORA Advisory Board

A bit before in this section, we have described the working structure of BDVA, composed of task forces with different interests. One of the most recent but also more prominent ones in the association is the so-called **ETAMI, revolving around trustworthy and ethical AI**.

ETAMI concentrates on making AI reliable and trustworthy by addressing its social, legal, and business risks, rethinking lifecycle models to enhance quality, and promoting auditing throughout the system's life cycle. Its solutions are piloted across various domains and supported by dedicated software tools. Fairness and non-discrimination, key to ethical AI, are still not fully understood, let alone integrated into corporate processes. Human oversight is technically complex, and robust data documentation tools are yet to be established.

The task force has been very productive in generating assets and content, all of them available here⁶. This has been, among other reasons, thanks to the chairmanship of the group, held by Patrick van der Smagt (ELTE, and until very recently also Volkswagen) and Gabriel González-Castañé (BDVA). Because of the relevance of the topic to PANDORA, at the beginning of our project we reached out to Patrick and offered him a position to be part of the project Advisory Board, which he kindly accepted. More information and Patrick's profile have been included in the corresponding deliverable (report on AB).

AI, Data, Robotics (ADRA) Forum

The ADRA Forum is the premier annual event organized by the AI, Data and Robotics Association (ADRA) in collaboration with the European Commission, and was held on the 4-5 November in Eindhoven (The Netherlands), with a focus on European Sovereignty in AI, Data and Robotics, a theme of critical importance in the advent of keeping both independence and competitiveness of the European economy in a period characterized by a growing role of and expectations around AI.

Session description “Achieving efficient trustworthy AI in the cloud-edge continuum”.

The session gave answers to the questions: How do we improve efficiency? How do we ensure trustworthiness? How do we make the best out of data? What changes when we extend across the cloud-edge continuum (CEC)? And how will the AI Act affect them?

AI-DAPT, EXTRA-BRAIN, MANOLO, PANDORA, and RAIDO projects joined hands in an effort to address these questions and shed light to the needs and challenges of efficient trustworthy AI in the cloud-edge continuum. Along the way, key experts from both academia and industry had a panel discussion to introduce several insights of how to achieve some of them in practice.

Together with the vibrant AI community, the workshop raised awareness on practical restrictions and major enablers for efficient trustworthy AI in the cloud edge continuum, covering important

⁶ <https://bdva.eu/task-forces/etami/>

topics that address data quality, data monitoring, benchmarking, explainable AI, self-adaptation, end-users' trust and of course environmental footprint.

Last but not least, the workshop explored the impact of the AI Act to the implementation and deployment of such AI systems across the cloud-edge, focusing on technical and legal implications.

Speakers:

Ricardo Simon Carbajo - MANOLO Project Coordinator
 Argyro Amidi - MANOLO (legal expert)
 Theodore Dalamagas - AI-DAPT Project Coordinator
 Marina Cugurra - AI-DAPT (legal expert)
 Maria Pateraki - PANDORA project coordinator
 Konstantinos Tserpes- PANDORA Deputy Project Coordinator
 Pawel Herman- EXTRA BRAIN Project Coordinator
 Moderator: Fabrizio Della Pace - EIT Digital

Figure 25: Promotional banner of the workshop featured by AI-ADAPT, EXTRA-BRAIN, MANOLO, PANDORA and RAIDO at the AI, Data and Robotics Forum

European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)

The BDVA flagship event EBDVF was described as part of the assets for PANDORA in our landscape analysis. Our project, even though still in its initial phase, has taken advantage of the sponsorship opportunities offered in the 2024 edition to engage with some relevant stakeholders and projects. The last edition took place from **2-4 October 2024 in Budapest**, Hungary and, as it is usual practice, was part of the EU Presidency agenda.

EBDVF in numbers: 468 participants along the 3 days, 71 partners and sponsors, 24 exhibition booths, ~180 speakers, 3 plenary sessions and 40 parallel sessions.

Manufacturing was a key sector explored in the conference, with several sessions on data sharing, data spaces and AI applied to this relevant domain of the EU economy. PANDORA capitalized the use cases of Philips and Siemens to share the overall vision of the project and expected deployments in such environments.

The session was a joint effort by projects PANDORA, CIRCULOOS and AIRedgio 5.0. In addition, it gave us the opportunity to engage with Manufacturing-X. PANDORA took the role of main organizer, moderator and speaker of the session.

Session description “Moving to the edge: the impact and implications of CEI continuum on Manufacturing”

Some of the top business trends in European Manufacturing include the transformation of the supply chain orchestration, sustainable operations, skills and workforce dynamics, harnessing the power of data in factory operations and unleashing the Power of AI with Generative AI. It is precisely in the area of data and AI where we have seen very advanced developments in the last years, but challenges still remain. One of the most interesting technical aspects has to do with the management of data operations where data is generated, bringing AI at the edge and making the computing continuum an underlying infrastructure companies need to deal with. This session will explore the impact of bringing AI at the edge, current approaches and technical shortcomings and will showcase some examples of how the CEI continuum is shaping use cases in both big and small industries. Three flagship projects like PANDORA, specialized in IoT-generated data and AI for smart space ecosystems (AIoT), with relevant industrial cases led by Philips and Siemens; AIREDGIO 5.0, focused on AI-at-the-Edge adoption by manufacturing SMEs, and CIRCULOOS, addressing the usage of such technologies to foster circularity in the SME context, will help us to understand what the current picture of AI at the edge and CEI continuum is for manufacturing in the EU.

Agenda

- Setting the scene: Major Trends in Manufacturing: Data, AI and Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) computing continuum (*Nuria de Lama, IDC*)
- AI at the edge: challenges and approach to develop AIoT. Industrial Use Case (*Maria Pateraki, PANDORA*)
- Technical approach to CEI continuum in the context of manufacturing SMEs. Industrial Use Case (*Alissa Zaccaria, AIREDGIO5.0*)
- CEI continuum and Circular Economy in manufacturing. Industrial Use Case (*Gábor Vicze, CIRCULOOS*)
- Implementing MANUFACTURING-X foundational framework in the CEI continuum of Didactic Factories (*Sergio Gusmeroli, Research Coordinator at Politecnico di Milano*)
- Panel discussion. CEI continuum for manufacturing, opportunities and challenges. Impact on Manufacturing Data Spaces and AI at the edge applications. Key takeaways.

Figure 26: Details of the EBDVF'2004 edition held in Budapest, including the PANDORA session with project coordinator Maria Pateraki (NTUA) as speaker and Nuria de Lama (IDC) as moderator.

Data Week Part III

The PANDORA project was presented during Data Week 2024 (Part III), held on **December 10, 2024**, at the Novotel Luxembourg Kirchberg in **Luxembourg**. The event was organized in collaboration with the Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), Netcompany-Intrasoft SA, and the Luxembourg National Data Service (LNDS).

This part of the Data Week included 20 sessions, more than 115 attendees and 46 speakers.

The main focus of the event was on fundamental elements of data value creation, with artificial intelligence (AI) serving as a pivotal tool in unlocking data value through various means. The event emphasized viewing data from an ecosystem perspective and fostering collaboration among multiple stakeholders, laying the groundwork needed for research excellence and competitiveness. In the last months, many of the discussions at BDVA have addressed topics related to AI and regulatory compliance. The program reflects precisely that focus. PANDORA was very relevant in this context, as one of the hot topics nowadays relates to synthetic data.

Georgios Bouloukakis, Associate Professor at Télécom SudParis, IP Paris and technical coordinator of PANDORA, contributed to the session “Manufacturing Data Spaces, as the Data Infrastructure for advanced AI applications”.

Session description:

Manufacturing Data Spaces, as the Data Infrastructure for advanced AI applications. The session aims at creating bridges between the three SMI Group pillars, namely Data Spaces, Digital Twins and AI, by exploring and discussing new challenges and opportunities related to the convergence of the three technologies in Manufacturing-driven business scenarios. After a short intro by DG CNECT G1 unit, the Data Spaces pillar will be introduced by the DS4.0 and SM4RTENANCE coordinator (INNOVALIA) in Digital EU programme; the Digital Twin pillar by IDTA implementation in Circular TwAIIn (FhG IOSB) in MiE+ADRA Horizon Europe; the AI pillar by two ADRA HEP projects of the cluster “Efficient and Trustworthy AI in the cloud-edge continuum” (AI-DAPT from

UNINOVA and PANDORA from NTUA) presenting their scientific / technological approaches applied to Manufacturing use cases. A panel discussion moderated by BDVA SMI group will conclude the session.

Agenda:

- Introduction: Davide Dalle Carbonare (ENGINEERING, BDVA SMI group co-chair) and a representative from the European Commission
- Carmen Polcaro (INNOVALIA): “Dynamic Asset Management and Predictive Maintenance: the SM4RTENANCE project” DS Pillar
- Ina Steinmetz (Fraunhofer IOSB): “AI-based IDTA DPP4.0 realization: challenges and lessons learned” Digital Twin Pillar
- Paulo Figueras (UNINOVA): “Data and AI Pipelines for Manufacturing and Industrial Robotics: the AI-DAPT project” AI Pillar
- Georgios Bouloukakis (IMT): “Efficient and Trustworthy AI in the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum: the PANDORA project (manufacturing pilots)” AI Pillar
- Valerio Franscolla (Intel)
- Panel Discussion

Figure 27: Promotional material of the session where PANDORA was presented at the Data Week'24

Webinar with EuCloudEdgeIoT.eu cluster and IPCEI-CIS

Being the computing continuum an important element of the underlying infrastructure of PANDORA, our project could not reject the proposal to take part in a webinar organized by the projects UNLOCK.CEI and CISERO, the first one being a CSA supporting the EuCloudEdgeIoT.eu cluster and the second one running the exploitation office of the initiative IPCEI-CIS.

The webinar took place on the **13 November 2024 15:00-16:30 CET**.

Session description “The future of Cloud and Edge technologies in the EU context: Market insights and sustainability roadmap”.

As cloud and edge technologies become increasingly pivotal for secure data processing and sharing, Europe's ability to lead in this domain is essential for economic resilience, innovation, and competitiveness. By fostering the development of scalable, federated, and secure cloud infrastructures, emerging initiatives such as the Important Project of Common European Interest on Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services (IPCEI-CIS) and the CISERO project aim to position Europe at the forefront of global digital advancements, ensuring the continent's leadership in emerging technologies that underpin the Digital Decade policy and overall sustainability goals.

In this context, several actions have been launched. An example is the UNLOCK-CEI project, one of the CSAs coordinating the EUCloudEdgeIoT initiative, as it represents a crucial link between the current state of the art of cloud, edge, and IoT technologies in the EU's framework. UNLOCK-CEI recently held its final event, providing a comprehensive mapping of the state-of-the-art demand & supply of cloud-edge-IoT applications. More recently, the CISERO project has been launched to support the successful implementation of IPCEI-CIS actions, facilitating collaboration among EU member states, industry leaders, and research organizations. Its mission is to coordinate resources, provide technical support, and build a robust business ecosystem to ensure the widespread adoption of cloud and edge computing solutions.

This event aims, on one side, to bring insights from the demand market of Cloud-Edge-IoT and, on the other side, to investigate how the joint efforts of Member States and industries through IPCEI-CIS projects can create its path towards the market. As a result, this event will discuss the key results of UNLOCK-CEI, which are synergistic with CISERO's goals. These include key trends, market pathways, frameworks, tools, and methodologies developed throughout the project. Moreover, considering the strategic role of AI in the CEI ecosystem (from a solutions perspective, market perspective and ecosystem players' perspective), there will be a panel discussion to focus on specific applications of AI on the computing continuum (in particular, AI at the edge) where pitches will be provided by the EU-funded projects working on the topic.

These outputs will be particularly valuable for CISERO, offering preliminary recommendations to address the challenges of cloud and edge integration and highlighting key remaining gaps. The legacy of UNLOCK-CEI could serve as a foundational element for creating CISERO's sustainability roadmap, which will support the IPCEI-CIS work in ensuring widespread adoption of next-generation technologies and cloud-to-edge solutions across Europe.

Agenda

Moderator: Claudio de Majo – Trust-IT Services, Italy

15:00 *Welcome and webinar introduction*

15:05 *Introducing the CISERO project in the IPCEI-CIS context* – Matthias Kuom/Sophia Herlmrich DLR Projektträger, Germany

15:15 *Navigating computing continuum: Demand market insights, dynamics and opportunities*– Golboo Pourabdollahian – IDC, Italy

15:35 Panel discussion “Edge AI for Europe's Cloud and Edge Future” – insights from EU-funded projects

- [AI REDGIO 5.0](#)
- [Manolo](#)
- [Pandora](#)

16:00 Q&A

16:10 Conclusion

Figure 28: Promotional detail of the webinar on the future of cloud and edge, with participation of PANDORA

4.4 International Collaboration

International collaborations are an important and integral part of this specific work package. This task spans from **Month 8 to Month 36** of the project's timeline. The primary objective is to promote knowledge sharing and worldwide scientific inclusion by leveraging international cooperation. So, this task will be completed with the completion of the project and the desirable should include:

- **Establishment of Collaborative Partnerships** with international organizations, institutions, and experts from different regions, including India and Canada.
- **Enhanced Knowledge Sharing** and exchange of expertise, leading to a broader understanding of trustworthy AI and energy efficiency in AIoT systems.
- **Increased Impact and Contribution** of the PANDORA project to the global research community and industry stakeholders.
- **Expansion of Project's Network** by integrating diverse perspectives and expertise from international partners, thereby enriching the project's outcomes and outputs.

The main partners to succeed the above, are:

- IISC (India),
- UOFT (Canada),
- NTUA (Greece)

In order for the consortium to succeed in the above desirable outcomes, main strategies should be developed.

- **Identify Key Conferences and forums:**

Partners should identify key conferences and forums, in these areas of India and Canada, related to trustworthy AI and energy efficiency in AIoT systems. Moreover, they should communicate with the organizers of those events in order to explore opportunities for collaboration, such as joint workshops, panels, or paper presentations.

- **Organize Workshops:**

Partners from India (IISC) and Canada (UOFT) with other consortium partners could organize workshops or seminars, either virtually or in-person, to facilitate knowledge sharing, discussion, and collaboration on specific research topics.

- **Collaborate on Research Issues:**

All consortium partners should actively collaborate on common research issues, such as joint research projects or initiatives involving PhD students.

- **Staff Exchange**

Through this exchange, participants from UOFT and IISC will have the opportunity to work directly with their counterparts at NTUA, sharing insights and methodologies related to trustworthy AI and energy efficiency in AIoT systems. This hands-on collaboration will not only enhance the skills and knowledge of the staff involved but also promote a deeper understanding of the research landscapes and technological innovations in both regions. Moreover, the exchange program will facilitate joint research projects, co-authored publications, and the development of innovative solutions, significantly contributing to the overall objectives of the PANDORA project. This initiative exemplifies the project's commitment to leveraging international cooperation for advancing scientific knowledge and technological development.

- **Engage with Industries:**

Collaboration with industry partners can lead to the application and commercialisation of research findings, as well as the exchange of valuable insights and resources. Create custom demos and prototypes showcasing the applications and benefits of PANDORA in these industries.

First and foremost, the consortium can expect the establishment of robust collaborative partnerships with esteemed international organizations, institutions, and experts from diverse regions. By developing these partnerships, the project plans to integrate a wide array of perspectives and expertise, as mentioned before. In summary, this specific task of the PANDORA project is expected to foster substantial international collaboration, enhance knowledge sharing, increase the project's global impact, expand its network, and achieve several measurable outcomes, ultimately contributing to the advancement of trustworthy AI and energy efficiency in AIoT systems.

5. Conclusions

The success of PANDORA depends on the excellent implementation of its technical work plan and the achievement of competitive performance in criteria of great value nowadays in AI systems. However, experience tells us that this is just a part of the story and other measures and achievements are needed to **ensure awareness, recognition and appetite for the results produced by the project.**

Early in this report we introduce those ideas with the example of the commercial fight that occurred between VHS vs. Betamax in the 1970s-80s, where Betamax had superior video quality, but VHS won due to longer recording times, cheaper licensing, and better distribution. A lot of other examples exist that illustrate the relevance of taking the right decisions at business level to gain penetration in the market, such as the battle between Apple iPod vs. Microsoft Zune. Around 1980s-90s, the same happened with IBM PC vs. Apple Macintosh or Google vs. Yahoo. More recently -so that younger readers, including those within our consortium, feel more familiar with-, Android and Windows Phone became competitors too. In this case Android grew through open-source adoption, strong app ecosystem, and partnerships with major manufacturers, while Windows Phone had a smooth OS but failed due to lack of app support, late market entry, and weak developer interest becoming the loser of mobile operating systems.

Thus, **beyond technical excellence represented by technical WPs in PANDORA, other ingredients matter to the success and impact of the project** as the former examples showcase:

- Ecosystem & Compatibility (VHS vs. Betamax, Android vs. Windows Phone)
- Partnerships & Industry Support (Blu-ray vs. HD DVD)
- Marketing & Branding (Tesla, iPod)
- Network Effects & Adoption (IBM PC vs. Mac, Google vs. Yahoo)
- Pricing & Accessibility (VHS, IBM PC, Android)

These are the aspects that will take our energy and effort within WP7.

First thing we look at is having **good communication towards internal and especially external stakeholders**, which requires **good branding, messaging, attractive and dynamic channels**, availability of updated and correct information for different groups of interest. It also requires bilateral relationships, **engaging trusted parties at the beginning, while focusing on potential customers later on for the validation of the product concepts**. Alignment with the demands of the market, going beyond the pilots that help us to technically validate the project is key, and for this, the project should **keep an eye on the market, competitors not only in the market (solutions in production) but also in the research arena, as it is the case of the sister projects to PANDORA**. Suitable **positioning, decisions on licenses, business models, pricing** and other activities to launch product/service(s) in the market add to the picture.

In D7.1, the first report of this WP, we have described the **pillars of the overall impact strategy of the project**; then, we dive deeper into each of the **four typologies of activities**:

- Dissemination and communication
- Exploitation and adoption of project results
- Collaboration, networking and clustering
- International cooperation

For each of them we depict the general context of the project, the methodological framework and activities that are part of our roadmap, and finally we report the extensive work that has already been done under each of them in the initial phase of the project, since **the best way of progressing -which includes making mistakes early enough- is learning by doing.**